

Steiner Formula for Convex Bodies

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Certificate of Examination

This is to certify that the dissertation titled “Steiner Formula for Convex Bodies” submitted by Mr. Pratik Sinha (Roll No. 16038) for the partial fulfilment of BS-MS dual degree programme of the Institute, has been examined by the thesis committee duly appointed by the Institute. The committee finds the work done by the candidate satisfactory and recommends that the report be accepted.

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Declaration

The work presented in this dissertation has been carried out by me under the guidance of Dr. Senthil Raani K S at the Indian Institute of Science Education and Research, Berhampur. This work has not been submitted in part or in full for a degree, a diploma, or a fellowship to any other university or institute. Whenever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with due acknowledgement of collaborative research and discussions. This thesis is a bonafide record of original work done by me and all sources listed within have been detailed in the bibliography.

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Pratik Sinha". The signature is written in a cursive style and is placed on a light yellow rectangular background.

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In my capacity as the supervisor of the candidate's project work, I certify that the above statements by the candidate are true to the best of my knowledge.

Dr. Senthil Raani K S
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Notations

- \mathbb{R} - the set of real numbers
- \mathbb{R}^n - the set of n -tuples of real numbers
- C^n - the set of nonempty compact subsets of \mathbb{R}^n
- \mathcal{K}^n - the set of convex bodies in \mathbb{R}^n
- Capital letters A, B etc. will denote sets
- Small letters x, y etc. will denote elements of sets
- Greek letters α, β will denote scalars
- $B(x, \rho) = \{y \in \mathbb{R}^n : |y - x| \leq \rho\}$
- \mathbb{S}^{n-1} - n -dimensional sphere of radius 1
- $\Sigma := \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{S}^{n-1}$
- For a set A , $\text{bd } A$ denotes the boundary of A
- For a function f , $f^+ = \max\{f, 0\}$ and $f^- = \max\{-f, 0\}$.
- a.e denotes almost everywhere
- For $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ $[x, y]$ denotes the line segment joining x and y , (x, y) denotes the line segment joining x and y with x and y omitted, $(x, y]$ is the line segment joining x and y with x omitted and similarly $[x, y)$ is the line segment joining x and y with y omitted.

Introduction

The Brunn–Minkowski theory is the classical core of the geometry of convex bodies. It originated with the thesis of Hermann Brunn in 1887 and is in its essential parts the creation of Hermann Minkowski, around the turn of the century. The well-known survey of Bonnesen and Fenchel in 1934 collected what was already an impressive body of results, though important developments were still to come, through the work of A. D. Aleksandrov and others in the thirties. In recent decades, the theory of convex bodies has expanded considerably; new topics have been developed and originally neglected branches of the subject have gained in interest. For instance, the combinatorial aspects, the theory of convex polytopes and the local theory of Banach spaces attract particular attention now. Nevertheless, the Brunn–Minkowski theory has remained of constant interest owing to its various new applications, its connections with other fields, and the challenge of some resistant open problems.

Aiming at a brief characterization of Brunn–Minkowski theory, one might say that it is the result of merging two elementary notions for point sets in Euclidean space: vector addition and volume. The vector addition of convex bodies, usually called Minkowski addition, has many facets of independent geometric interest. Combined with volume, it leads to the fundamental Brunn–Minkowski inequality and the notion of mixed volumes. The latter satisfy a series of inequalities which, due to their flexibility, solve many extremal problems and yield several uniqueness results. Looking at mixed volumes from a local point of view, one is led to mixed area measures. Quermassintegrals, or Minkowski functionals, and their local versions, surface area measures and curvature measures, are a special case of mixed volumes and mixed area measures. They are related to the differential geometry of convex hypersurfaces and to integral geometry.

In this dissertation we will discuss about the Steiner formula for convex

bodies. For generally "smooth" bodies like the sphere we can easily find out curvature of the surface by elementary differential geometry. For bodies which are "not smooth", like the cuboid which have "sharp" edges the notion of curvature defined in elementary differential geometry is not useful and does not exist. The Steiner formula helps us in this regard and helps us give a notion of curvature via curvature measure and surface area measure to "not smooth" convex bodies like the cuboid.

Chapter 1

Preliminaries

In this chapter we define some basic structures of Mathematics and state some fundamental properties which lay down the foundation for discussion on convex bodies. For the sake of brevity we skip the proofs of the results. Interested readers may find detailed proofs and discussion of the concepts and results in Measure Theory and Fine Properties of Functions by Lawrence C. Evans and Measure Theory by Paul R Halmos.

Definition 1.0.1. Let X be a set and $\mathcal{P}(X)$ be its power set. A subset $\Theta \subset \mathcal{P}(X)$ is called a σ -algebra if it has the following three properties:

1. If $S \in \Theta$, then its complement, $X \setminus S \in \Theta$
2. $X \in \Theta$
3. If $(S_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a collection of sets such that $S_i \in \Theta$ for $i \in \mathbb{N}$ then

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} S_i \in \Theta$$

Definition 1.0.2. Let X be a set and Θ be a σ -algebra over X . A map from Θ to the extended real number line is called a measure if it satisfies the following:

1. For all $E \in \Theta$, we have $\mu(E) \geq 0$
2. $\mu(\emptyset) = 0$

3. For all countable collections $(E_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ of pairwise disjoint sets in Θ ,

$$\mu\left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} E_k\right) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \mu(E_k)$$

A set $A \subset X$ is called μ -measurable if $A \in \Theta$.

Definition 1.0.3. A topological space is a set X together with a collection τ of subsets of X which satisfies the following conditions:

1. The empty set \emptyset is in τ .
2. X is in τ .
3. The intersection of a finite number of sets in τ is also in τ .
4. The union of an arbitrary number of sets in τ is also in τ .

For the sake of brevity we denote the topological space (X, τ) by X itself.

Definition 1.0.4. A metric on a set X is a function $d : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ where $[0, \infty)$ is the set of non-negative real numbers and for all $x, y, z \in X$, the following are satisfied:

1. $d(x, y) = 0$ iff $x = y$.
2. $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$.
3. $d(x, y) \leq d(x, z) + d(z, y)$

Definition 1.0.5. Let X be a topological space. The function $f : X \rightarrow [-\infty, \infty]$ is called lower semicontinuous at $x_0 \in X$ if for every real $y < f(x_0)$ there exists a neighbourhood U of x_0 such that $y < f(u)$ for all $u \in U$.

A function is called lower semicontinuous if it is lower semicontinuous at every point of its domain.

Definition 1.0.6. A metric space is an ordered pair of set M and metric $d : M \times M \rightarrow [0, \infty)$.

A metric space is an example of topological space.

Proposition 1.0.1. Let $f : X \rightarrow [-\infty, \infty]$ be a lower semicontinuous function. Let $(x_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence in X such that $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} x_i = x$ where $x \in X$. Then

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} f(x_i) \geq f(x)$$

Theorem 1.0.1. Let $(A_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a collection of μ -measurable sets.

- The sets $\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_k$ and $\cap_{i=1}^{\infty} A_k$ are μ -measurable.
- If $A_1 \subset A_2 \subset \dots \subset A_k \subset A_{k+1} \subset \dots$, then

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \mu(A_k) = \mu(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_k)$$

- If $A_1 \supset A_2 \supset \dots \supset A_k \supset A_{k+1} \supset \dots$, then

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \mu(A_k) = \mu(\cap_{i=1}^{\infty} A_k)$$

Definition 1.0.7. Let X be a set and Y be a topological space and μ be a measure on X . A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called μ -measurable if for each open $U \subset Y$, $f^{-1}(U)$ is μ -measurable.

Definition 1.0.8. Given a measure space (X, U, μ) a function f is called a simple function if it satisfies the following:

- The domain of f is contained in U
- f is μ -measurable on its domain
- the range of f is a finite subset of \mathbb{R}

Definition 1.0.9. If g is a nonnegative, simple, μ -measurable function, we define

$$\int g d\mu := \sum_{0 \leq y \leq \infty} y \mu(g^{-1}\{y\})$$

Definition 1.0.10. If g is a simple μ -measurable function and either $\int g^+ d\mu < \infty$ or $\int g^- d\mu < \infty$, we call g a μ -integrable simple function and define

$$\int g d\mu = \int g^+ d\mu - \int g^- d\mu$$

Definition 1.0.11. Let X be a set and $f : X \rightarrow [-\infty, \infty]$ be a μ -measurable function. We define the upper integral as

$$\int^* f d\mu := \inf\left\{\int g d\mu \mid g \text{ a } \mu\text{-integrable simple function with } g \geq f \text{ } \mu \text{ a.e.}\right\}$$

and the lower integral as

$$\int_* f d\mu := \sup\left\{\int g d\mu \mid g \text{ a } \mu\text{-integrable simple function with } g \leq f \text{ } \mu \text{ a.e.}\right\}$$

Definition 1.0.12. A μ -measurable function $f : X \rightarrow [-\infty, \infty]$ is called μ -integrable if $\int^* f d\mu = \int_* f d\mu$, in which case we write

$$\int f d\mu := \int^* f d\mu = \int_* f d\mu$$

Definition 1.0.13. A function $f : X \rightarrow [-\infty, \infty]$ is called μ -summable if f is μ -integrable and

$$\int f d\mu < \infty$$

Theorem 1.0.2. Let $f_k : X \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ be μ -measurable ($k = 1, 2, \dots$). Then

$$\int \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} f_k d\mu \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int f_k d\mu$$

Theorem 1.0.3. Let $g, (g_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be μ -summable and $f, (f_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be μ -integrable functions. Suppose $|f_k| \leq g_k$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots$), $f_k \rightarrow f$ μ a.e. (by saying a property holds almost everywhere we mean that the set on which the property doesn't hold has measure 0.) and

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int g_k d\mu = \int g d\mu.$$

Then

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int |f_k - f| d\mu = 0$$

Definition 1.0.14. Let X and Y be sets. Let μ be a measure on X and ν be a measure on Y . We define the product measure $\mu \times \nu : \mathcal{P}(X \times Y) \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ by setting for each $S \subset X \times Y$:

$$(\mu \times \nu)(S) := \inf\left\{\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \mu(A_i)\nu(B_i)\right\}$$

where the infimum is taken over all μ -measurable sets $A_i \subset X$ and ν -measurable sets $B_i \subset Y$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots$) such that

$$S \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_i \times B_i).$$

The measure $\mu \times \nu$ is called the product measure of μ and ν .

Definition 1.0.15. The Lebesgue outer measure on \mathbb{R} is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}^{*1}(A) = \inf \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{diam } C_i \mid A \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} C_i, C_i \subset \mathbb{R} \right\}$$

where $A \subset \mathbb{R}$.

Lemma 1.0.1. The set \mathcal{A} of all sets $E \subset \mathbb{R}$ which satisfy for all $A \subset \mathbb{R}$

$$\mathcal{L}^{*1}(A) = \mathcal{L}^{*1}(A \cap E) + \mathcal{L}^{*1}(A \cap E^c)$$

forms a σ -algebra

Definition 1.0.16. The Lebesgue measure $\mathcal{L}^1 : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}^1(E) = \mathcal{L}^{*1}(E)$$

Definition 1.0.17. We define inductively \mathcal{L}^n on \mathbb{R}^n as

$$\mathcal{L}^n = \mathcal{L}^1 \times \dots \times \mathcal{L}^1 \text{ n times.}$$

Definition 1.0.18. The dimension of a set $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is defined to be

$$\dim A = \inf \{ 0 \leq s < \infty \mid \mathcal{L}^s(A) = 0 \}$$

Definition 1.0.19. Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ a function $f : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is called Lipschitz provided

$$|f(x) - f(y)| \leq C|x - y|$$

for some constant $C \in \mathbb{R}$ and all $x, y \in A$.

Theorem 1.0.4. Let $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ be Lipschitz, $n \leq m$. Then for each \mathcal{L}^n -summable function $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} g(x) J f(x) dx = \int_{\mathbb{R}^m} \sum_{x \in f^{-1}\{y\}} g(x) d\mathcal{L}^m(y)$$

Lemma 1.0.2. Let $K \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Then $\dim(\text{bd } K) \leq \dim K - 1$.

Chapter 2

Convex Bodies \mathcal{K}^3 on \mathbb{R}^3

In this chapter we define convex sets and convex bodies and state certain results which are useful in laying down the foundation of future discussions. We show that the set of Convex Bodies forms a metric space and a measure space under a suitably defined metric and measure respectively. In the first section we deal precisely with the said definitions of convex sets and convex bodies while showing a result which helps us develop an intuitive idea about convexity. In the second section we define a metric on the set of convex bodies and show how under this metric the set of convex bodies forms a complete metric space, as this will facilitate arguments regarding convergent sequence of convex bodies which will be used to show in section 4 that convex bodies form a measure space under the measure defined, while in section 3 we define the metric projection which will be used to introduce the geometry of convex bodies and will be used to conclude the weakly continuous property of the measure defined on convex bodies. All the properties concluded in section 4 will be used in chapter 3 to define curvature and surface area measures and how to calculate them for certain cases.

2.1 Convex Sets

Definition 2.1.1. A set $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is called a convex set if for any $x, y \in A$ the segment $[x, y]$ between them is also in A .

$$\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y \in A \quad \forall x, y \in A$$

where $\lambda \in [0, 1]$

Figure 2.1: A convex set in \mathbb{R}^2 $A = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid 2x^2 + 3y^2 \leq 1\}$

Definition 2.1.2. A convex body is a non-empty compact and convex subset of \mathbb{R}^n

Figure 2.2: A convex body $B = \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid x^2 + y^2 \leq 1, -1 \leq z \leq 1\}$

Definition 2.1.3. For any set A, B we define their Minkowski sum as

$$A + B := \{a + b : a \in A, b \in B\}$$

Figure 2.3: Minkowski sum of a Circle and a Triangle

Definition 2.1.4. The scalar multiple of a set is defined as

$$\lambda A = \{\lambda a : a \in A\}$$

Figure 2.4: $A = 2B$

Lemma 2.1.1. Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be convex. If $x \in \text{int } A$ and $y \in \text{cl } A$, then

$$[x, y) \subset \text{int } A.$$

Proof.

Case 1: $x \in \text{int } A$ and $y \in A \cap \text{cl } A$

Let $z = (1 - \lambda)y + \lambda x$ with $0 < \lambda < 1$. Since $x \in \text{int } A$, there exists some $\rho > 0$ such that $B(x, \rho) \subset A$. Let $U := B(o, \rho)$ and $w \in \lambda U + z$, that is, $w = \lambda u + z$ for some $u \in U$. Since $x + u \in B(x, \rho) \subset A$, $y \in A \cap \text{cl } A$ and A is convex, we have $w = (1 - \lambda)y + \lambda(x + u) \in A$. Thus $\lambda U + z \subset A$ and hence $z = (1 - \lambda)y + \lambda x \in \text{int } A$. Hence $[x, y) \subset \text{int } A$.

Case 2: $x \in \text{int } A$ and $y \notin A$, $y \in \text{cl } A$

Let $V := [\lambda/(1 - \lambda)]U + y$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} V &= \frac{\lambda}{1 - \lambda}U + y = \frac{\lambda}{1 - \lambda}B(o, \rho) + y \\ &= B(o, \frac{\lambda\rho}{1 - \lambda}) + y = B(y, \frac{\lambda\rho}{1 - \lambda}) \end{aligned}$$

Thus V is a neighbourhood centred at y . Since every neighbourhood of a boundary point of A contains at least one point inside A and one point outside A , there exists some $a \in (\text{int } A) \cap V$. Thus we have $a = [\lambda/(1 - \lambda)]u + y$ for some $u \in U$. Thus $(1 - \lambda)a - \lambda u = y(1 - \lambda)$ which implies $\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y = (1 - \lambda)a + \lambda(x - u)$. As $a \in \text{int } A$ and $(x - u) \in \text{int } A$, and A is convex, $(1 - \lambda)a + \lambda(x - u) \in \text{int } A$. As λ was arbitrarily chosen, we conclude $[x, y) \subset \text{int } A$.

□

Definition 2.1.5. The point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a convex combination of points $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^n$ if $\exists \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i x_i \quad \text{with } \lambda_i \geq 0 \ (i = 1, \dots, n), \quad \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i = 1$$

For $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ the set of all convex combinations of finitely many elements of A is called the convex hull of A . It is denoted by $\text{conv } A$.

Figure 2.5: The shaded region denotes the convex combination of points u_1 , u_2 and u_3

Definition 2.1.6. The point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a affine combination of points $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^n$ if $\exists \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i x_i \quad \text{with } \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i = 1.$$

For $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ the set of all affine combinations of finitely many elements of A is called the affine hull of A . It is denoted as $\text{aff } A$.

Figure 2.6: The plane including the shaded area is the affine combination of point a , b , c and d

Definition 2.1.7. The point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a positive combination of $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ if there exists $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k \geq 0$ such that

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i x_i$$

where $\lambda_i \in \mathbb{R}$.

For a set $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ we denote by $\text{pos } A$ the set of positive combinations of finitely many elements of A .

2.2 \mathcal{K}^3 is complete

In this section we will define a metric on the set of compact subsets of \mathbb{R}^n .

Definition 2.2.1. The Hausdorff distance between $K, L \in C^n$ is given as follows

$$\delta(K, L) := \max\{\sup_{x \in K} \inf_{y \in L} |x - y|, \sup_{x \in L} \inf_{y \in K} |x - y|\}$$

Now we will show that this is indeed a metric on C^n

Proposition 2.2.1. δ is a metric on C^n .

Proof. Let $\delta(K, L) = 0$. We show this implies $K = L$.

$$\Rightarrow \sup_{x \in K} \inf_{y \in L} |x - y| = 0 \text{ and } \sup_{x \in L} \inf_{y \in K} |x - y| = 0$$

$$\sup_{x \in K} \inf_{y \in L} |x - y| = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \inf_{y \in L} |x - y| = 0 \quad \forall x \in K$$

$$\Rightarrow \forall x \in K \exists y \in L \text{ such that } |x - y| = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \forall x \in K \exists y \in L \text{ such that } x = y$$

$$\text{Therefore, } x \in K \Rightarrow x \in L$$

$$\Rightarrow K \subset L$$

Interchanging the roles of K and L we obtain $L \subset K$

Thus we conclude $K = L$. Now, let $K = L$. We show that $\delta(K, L) = 0$.

$$K = L$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow \inf_{y \in L} |x - y| = 0 \text{ where } x \in K \\ &\Rightarrow \sup_{x \in K} \inf_{y \in L} |x - y| = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $\sup_{x \in L} \inf_{y \in K} |x - y| = 0$. Hence, $\delta(K, L) = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(K, L) &= \max\{\sup_{x \in K} \inf_{y \in L} |x - y|, \sup_{x \in L} \inf_{y \in K} |x - y|\} \\ &= \max\{\sup_{x \in L} \inf_{y \in K} |x - y|, \sup_{x \in K} \inf_{y \in L} |x - y|\} \\ &= \delta(L, K) \end{aligned}$$

We now show that Hausdorff metric satisfies triangle inequality.

Let $K, L, M \in \mathcal{K}^n$

For $a, b, c \in K, L, M$ respectively, we have

$$\inf_{c \in M} |a - c| \leq |a - b| + \inf_{c \in M} |b - c| \leq |a - b| + \sup_{b \in M} \inf_{c \in M} |b - c| \leq |a - b| + \delta(L, M)$$

for all $b \in L$. Taking infimum over $b \in L$ we have

$$\inf_{c \in M} |a - c| \leq \inf_{b \in L} |a - b| + \delta(L, M).$$

Now, taking supremum over $a \in K$ we have

$$\sup_{a \in K} \inf_{c \in M} |a - c| \leq \sup_{a \in K} \inf_{b \in L} |a - b| + \delta(L, M) \leq \delta(K, L) + \delta(L, M).$$

Similarly, $\sup_{a \in M} \inf_{c \in K} |a - c| \leq \delta(K, L) + \delta(L, M)$

Thus, we conclude $\delta(K, M) \leq \delta(K, L) + \delta(L, M)$.

□

We give another definition of Hausdorff distance as follows

Proposition 2.2.2. *The Hausdorff distance between $K, L \in C^n$ is also given as*

$$\delta(K, L) = \min\{\lambda \geq 0 \mid K \subset L + \epsilon B^n, L \subset K + \epsilon B^n\}$$

Proof. Let us denote the RHS of the above as α .

By Definition 1.3.1, $K \subset L + \alpha B^n$, $L \subset K + \alpha B^n$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} x \in K &\Rightarrow x \in L + \alpha B^n. \\ &\Rightarrow x = y + \alpha b \text{ with suitable } y \in L \text{ and } b \in B^n. \\ &\Rightarrow |x - y| \leq \alpha \\ &\text{Therefore } \inf_{y \in L} |x - y| \leq \alpha \end{aligned}$$

As x was arbitrarily chosen, $\sup_{x \in K} \inf_{y \in L} |x - y| \leq \alpha$

Changing the roles of K and L we obtain, $\sup_{x \in L} \inf_{y \in K} |x - y| \leq \alpha$ and thus conclude $\delta(K, L) \leq \alpha$

Let $0 < \lambda < \alpha$ and, say, $K \not\subset L + \lambda B^n$. Then $x \notin L + \lambda B^n$ for some $x \in K$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} |x - y| &\geq \lambda \forall y \in L. \\ &\Rightarrow \inf_{y \in L} |x - y| \geq \lambda \\ &\Rightarrow \sup_{x \in K} \inf_{y \in L} |x - y| \geq \lambda \end{aligned}$$

$\delta(K, L) \geq \lambda$ By Definition 1.3.1 because $\lambda < \alpha$ was arbitrary, we conclude $\delta(K, L) \geq \alpha$.

Thus we conclude $\delta(K, L) = \alpha$ which implies

$$\delta(K, L) = \min\{\lambda \geq 0 \mid K \subset L + \lambda B^n, L \subset K + \lambda B^n\}.$$

□

Now we will show that (C^n, δ) is a complete metric space. The following proposition gives us the how to get the limit of a certain type of convergent sequence of sets in (C^n, δ) . This result will be used in proving the completeness of (C^n, δ) .

Proposition 2.2.3. *Let $\{K_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a decreasing sequence, that is, $K_i \subset K_{i+1}$. Then*

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} K_i = \bigcap_{i \in \mathbb{N}} K_i.$$

Proof. Assuming the assertion is false. Then for some fixed $\epsilon > 0$

$$\delta(K_m, K) \geq \epsilon \quad \forall m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

As K_m is compact, there exists $x \in K_m$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \inf_{y \in K} |x - y| &\geq \epsilon \\ \Rightarrow |x - y| &\geq \epsilon \quad \forall y \in K \end{aligned}$$

In, particular,

$$\begin{aligned} d(K, x) &\geq \epsilon \\ \Rightarrow x &\in \{z \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid d(K, z) \geq \epsilon\} \\ \Rightarrow x &\in (K + \epsilon B^n)^c \\ \Rightarrow x &\notin K + \epsilon B^n \\ \Rightarrow K_m &\not\subset K + \epsilon B^n \end{aligned}$$

Define $A_m := K_m \setminus \text{int}(K + \epsilon B^n)$. Hence $\{A_m\}$ is a decreasing sequence of compact sets and hence has a nonempty intersection

$$A := \bigcap_{m \in \mathbb{N}} A_m.$$

Clearly $A \cap K \neq \emptyset$. But $A_m \subset K_m$ implies $A \subset K$. This is a contradiction. Hence our assumption was wrong and the assertion in the proposition holds. \square

Proposition 2.2.4. (C^n, δ) is complete .

Proof. Let $\{K_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a Cauchy sequence in C^n . Define $A_m := \text{cl} \bigcap_{i=m}^{\infty} K_i$. As $\{K_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a Cauchy sequence, for given $\epsilon > 0 \exists N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(K_n, K_m) &< \epsilon \quad \forall m, n \geq N \\ \Rightarrow K_m &\subset K_n + \epsilon B^n \end{aligned}$$

In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} K_m &\subset K_N + \epsilon B^n \\ \Rightarrow \bigcup_{i=m}^{\infty} K_i &\subset K_N + \epsilon B^n \end{aligned}$$

From this we can conclude that A_m is a decreasing sequence of non-empty compact sets.

Hence $A_m \rightarrow A := \bigcap_{i \in \mathbb{N}} A_i$ as $j \rightarrow \infty$ by Proposition 1.3.3. Thus for a given $\epsilon > 0$ there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(A_m, A) &< \epsilon \quad \forall m \geq n_0 \\ &\Rightarrow A_m \subset A + \epsilon B^n \\ &\Rightarrow K_i \subset A + \epsilon B^n. \end{aligned}$$

For $i, m \geq \max\{n_0, N\} = n_1$ $A \subset K_i + \epsilon B^n$ that implies $\delta(A, K_i) < \epsilon$ for $i \geq n_1$. Hence the assertion follows. \square

Theorem 2.2.1. \mathcal{K}^n is a closed subset of C^n .

Proof. We will prove that $C^n \setminus \mathcal{K}^n$ is open. Let $K \in C^n \setminus \mathcal{K}^n$. Then there are points $x, y \in K$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$, $\epsilon > 0$ such that $B(z, \epsilon) \cap K = \emptyset$ for $z = (1 - \lambda)x + \lambda y$. Let $K' \in C^n$ satisfying $\delta(K, K') < \epsilon$. There are points $x', y' \in K'$ which satisfy $|x - x'| < \epsilon/2$ and $|y - y'| < \epsilon/2$, hence the point $z' := (1 - \lambda)x' + \lambda y'$ satisfying $|z - z'| < \epsilon/2$. If $z' \in K'$, then there is a point $w \in K$ with $|w - z'| < \epsilon/2$ which implies $|w - z| < \epsilon$ which is a contradiction. Thus K' is not convex. Thus K is an interior point of $C^n \setminus \mathcal{K}^n$. As K is an arbitrarily chosen set, $C^n \setminus \mathcal{K}^n$ is open. Thus, \mathcal{K}^n is closed. \square

As the closed subset of a complete space is complete we can conclude that (\mathcal{K}^n, δ) is complete.

2.3 Metric Projection

Lemma 2.3.1. Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a non-empty closed convex set. To each $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ there exists a unique point $p(A, x) \in A$ satisfying

$$|x - p(A, x)| \leq |x - y| \quad \forall y \in A.$$

Proof. For suitable $\rho > 0$ the set $B(x, \rho) \cap A$ is compact and nonempty, since the intersection of a closed and compact set is compact. Hence the continuous function $y \mapsto |x - y|$ attains its minimum on $B(x, \rho) \cap A$ due to Extreme Value Theorem, say at $y_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Thus $|x - y_0| \leq |x - y|$ for all $y \in A$. Let $y_1 \in \mathbb{R}^n$

also satisfy $|x - y_1| \leq |x - y|$ for all $y \in A$. Let $z := (y_0 + y_1)/2$. $z \in A$ since A is convex. Then

$$\begin{aligned} |x - z| &= \left| x - \frac{y_0 + y_1}{2} \right| = \left| \frac{x - y_0}{2} + \frac{x - y_1}{2} \right| \\ &\leq \left| \frac{x - y_0}{2} \right| + \left| \frac{x - y_1}{2} \right| \\ &\leq \left| \frac{x - y_0}{2} \right| + \left| \frac{x - y_0}{2} \right| \\ &= |x - y_0| \end{aligned}$$

This is true only if $y_0 = z$. Thus we have $y_0 = \frac{y_0 + y_1}{2}$ which implies $y_0 = y_1$. Thus $y_0 =: p(A, x)$ is unique. \square

Definition 2.3.1. Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a non-empty closed convex set. To each $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ there exists a unique point $p(A, x) \in A$ satisfying

$$|x - p(A, x)| \leq |x - y| \quad \forall y \in A.$$

In this way, the map $p(A, \cdot) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow A$ is called the metric projection map or nearest point map.

Example: Let $A = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid 0 \leq x \leq 1, 0 \leq y \leq 1\}$. The nearest point map is as follows

$$p(A, (x, y)) = \begin{cases} (x, y) & (x, y) \in A \\ (x, 1) & 0 \leq x \leq 1, y \geq 1 \\ (x, 0) & 0 \leq x \leq 1, y \leq 0 \\ (0, y) & x \leq 0, 0 \leq y \leq 1 \\ (1, y) & x \geq 1, 0 \leq y \leq 1 \\ (0, 0) & x \leq 0, y \leq 0 \\ (0, 1) & x \leq 0, y \geq 1 \\ (1, 0) & x \geq 1, y \leq 1 \\ (1, 1) & x \geq 1, y \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.3.2. We define the distance between a point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and a nonempty closed convex set A as

$$d(A, x) := |x - p(A, x)|.$$

Definition 2.3.3. For $x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus A$ the unit vector pointing from A to x is denoted by

$$u(A, x) := \frac{x - p(A, x)}{|x - p(A, x)|}.$$

$d(A, x) \neq 0$ since $x \notin A$ as for $x \in A$, $p(A, x) = x$ and thus $d(A, x) = 0$.

Example: For $A = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid 0 \leq x \leq 1, 0 \leq y \leq 1\}$ the outer normal vector are described as

$$u(A, x) = \begin{cases} (0, 1) & 0 \leq x \leq 1, y \geq 1 \\ (1, 0) & 0 \leq x \leq 1, y \leq 0 \\ (0, 1) & x \leq 0, 0 \leq y \leq 1 \\ (1, 0) & x \geq 0, 0 \leq y \leq 1 \\ \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{x^2+y^2}}, \frac{y}{\sqrt{x^2+y^2}} \right) & x \leq 0, y \leq 0 \\ \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{x^2+(y-1)^2}}, \frac{y-1}{\sqrt{x^2+(y-1)^2}} \right) & x \leq 0, y \geq 1 \\ \left(\frac{x-1}{\sqrt{(x-1)^2+y^2}}, \frac{y}{\sqrt{(x-1)^2+y^2}} \right) & x \geq 1, y \leq 1 \\ \left(\frac{x-1}{\sqrt{(x-1)^2+(y-1)^2}}, \frac{y-1}{\sqrt{(x-1)^2+(y-1)^2}} \right) & x \geq 1, y \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

Remark 1. For a sphere the outer normal vector and normal vector to the sphere are equal.

Definition 2.3.4. The ray through x with end point $p(A, x)$ is defined as follows

$$R(A, x) := \{p(A, x) + \lambda u(A, x) : \lambda \geq 0\}$$

Theorem 2.3.1. The metric projection is contracting, that is ,

$$|p(A, x) - p(A, y)| \leq |x - y| \text{ for } x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Proof. If $p(A, x) = p(A, y)$, then we are done since we know

$$|x - y| \geq 0 = |p(A, x) - p(A, y)| \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Hence let $v := p(A, x) - p(A, y) \neq 0$.

We define the function f as $f(t) := |x - (p(A, x) + tv)|^2$. It has a minimum at $t = 0$ by definition of metric projection.

$\Rightarrow f'(0) \geq 0$ and

$$\begin{aligned} f(t) &= |x - (p(A, x) + tv)|^2 \\ &= \langle x - (p(A, x) + tv), x - (p(A, x) + tv) \rangle \\ &= \langle (x - p(A, x)) - tv, (x - p(A, x)) - tv \rangle \\ &= \langle x - p(A, x), x - p(A, x) \rangle - 2t \langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle + t^2 \langle v, v \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\Rightarrow f'(t) &= -2\langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle + 2t\langle v, v \rangle \\ f'(0) &= -2\langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle.\end{aligned}$$

Thus $-2\langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle \geq 0 \Rightarrow \langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle \leq 0$

We define function g as $g(t) := |y - (p(A, y) - tv)|^2$

Applying the same argument to g as we did for f we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\langle y - p(A, y), v \rangle &\geq 0 \text{ and } \langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle \leq 0 \\ \Rightarrow \langle y - p(A, y), v \rangle - \langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle &\geq 0 \\ \Rightarrow \langle y - x - p(A, y) + p(A, x), v \rangle &\geq 0 \\ \Rightarrow \langle y - x - v, v \rangle &\geq 0 \\ \Rightarrow \langle y - x, v \rangle - \langle v, v \rangle &\geq 0 \\ \Rightarrow \langle y - x, v \rangle &\geq \langle v, v \rangle \\ \Rightarrow -2\langle y - x, v \rangle &\leq -2\langle v, v \rangle \\ \Rightarrow \langle y - x, y - x \rangle - 2\langle y - x, v \rangle + \langle v, v \rangle &\leq \langle y - x, y - x \rangle - \langle v, v \rangle \\ \Rightarrow \langle y - x - v, y - x - v \rangle &\leq \langle y - x, y - x \rangle - \langle v, v \rangle \\ \Rightarrow |y - x|^2 - |v|^2 &\geq |y - x - v|^2 \geq 0 \\ \Rightarrow |y - x|^2 &\geq |v|^2 \\ \Rightarrow |y - x| &\geq |v|\end{aligned}$$

We know that $v = p(A, x) - p(A, y)$, hence we conclude

$$|x - y| \geq |p(A, x) - p(A, y)|$$

□

Proposition 2.3.1 will be used to show that the measure of the outer parallel body is weakly continuous. All the relevant details and subsequent use of the proposition will be discussed in section 2.4.

Lemma 2.3.2. Let S be the boundary of a ball containing A in its interior. Then $p(A, S) = \text{bd } A$.

Proof. The inclusion $p(A, S) \subset \text{bd } A$ is trivial. Let $x \in \text{bd } A$. For $i \in \mathbb{N}$ choose x_i in the ball bounded by S such that $x_i \notin A$ and $|x - x_i| < 1/i$. From Theorem 1.3.1 we have

$$|x - p(A, x_i)| = |p(A, x) - p(A, x_i)| \leq |x - x_i| \leq 1/i$$

The ray $R(A, x_i)$ meets S in a point y_i and we have $p(A, y_i) = p(A, x_i)$, hence $|x - p(A, y_i)| < 1/i$. A subsequence $(y_{i_j})_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to a point $y \in S$. From

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} p(A, y_i) = x$$

and the continuity of the metric projection we see that $x = p(A, y)$. Thus

$$\text{bd}A \subset p(A, S).$$

Hence the assertion follows. □

From the definition of Hausdorff distance, we show that the metric projection is continuous in both variables in the following proposition.

Proposition 2.3.1. *Let $K, L \in \mathcal{K}^n, x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and put $D := \text{diam}(K \cup L \cup \{x, y\})$. Then*

$$|p(K, x) - p(L, y)| \leq |x - y| + \sqrt{5D\delta(K, L)}.$$

Proof. From Theorem 2.3.1 we obtain

$$|p(L, x) - p(L, y)| \leq |x - y|.$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |p(K, x) - p(L, y)| &= |p(K, x) - p(L, x) + p(L, x) - p(L, y)| \\ &\leq |p(K, x) - p(L, x)| + |p(L, x) - p(L, y)| \text{ By triangle inequality} \\ &\leq |p(K, x) - p(L, x)| + |x - y|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus it is enough to show that

$$|p(K, x) - p(L, x)| \leq \sqrt{5D\delta(K, L)}.$$

Suppose $x \in K \cap L$. Then $|p(K, x) - p(L, x)| = 0$ and we are done.

Let $x \notin K$ and $x = p(K, x) + d u(K, x)$ where $d \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\delta(K, L) = \delta$. By the definition of Hausdorff distance, $B(x, \delta)$ intersects L therefore $B(p(K, x), \delta)$ contains a point $l \in L$. Thus $d(l, p(K, x)) \leq \delta$

Hence,

$$d(l, x) \leq d(l, p(K, x)) + d(p(K, x), x)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \delta + d \\ \Rightarrow d(L, x) &\leq d + \delta \\ \Rightarrow p(L, x) &\in B(x, d + \delta) \end{aligned}$$

Let $u(K, x) = u$ be the outer normal vector and $H_{u,0}^- = H^- p(K, x)$, $p(L, x)$ are interior points of $B(x, d + \delta)$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle p(L, x) - p(K, x), u(K, x) \rangle &\leq d + \delta \\ \langle p(L, x) - p(K, x), u(K, x) \rangle &> -(d + \delta) \langle u(K, x), u(K, x) \rangle \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

From here we see that $\exists y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} p(L, x) &= y + \delta u \text{ and} \\ \langle y - p(K, x), u(K, x) \rangle &\leq 0 \\ \Rightarrow p(L, x) &\in H^- + \delta u(K, x) \\ \Rightarrow p(L, x) &\in B(x, d + \delta) + (H^- + \delta u(K, x)) \langle p(L, x) - x, p(L, x) - x \rangle \leq (d + \delta)^2 \\ \langle p(L, x) - p(K, x) - \delta u, p(L, x) - p(K, x) - \delta u \rangle &\leq d^2 + \delta^2 + 2d\delta \\ |p(L, x) - p(K, x)|^2 - 2d \langle p(L, x) - p(K, x), u \rangle &\leq d^2 + \delta^2 + 2d\delta \\ |p(L, x) - p(K, x)|^2 &\leq 2d \langle p(L, x) - p(K, x), u \rangle + \delta^2 + 2d\delta \\ \text{But } p(L, x) - \delta u &\in H^- \\ \langle p(L, x) - \delta u - p(K, x), u \rangle &\leq 0 \\ \langle p(L, x) - p(K, x), u \rangle &\leq \delta \langle u, u \rangle \\ \langle p(L, x) - p(K, x), u \rangle &\leq \delta \\ \text{Hence } |p(L, x) - p(K, x)|^2 &\leq 2d\delta + \delta^2 + 2d\delta = 4d\delta + \delta^2 \\ |p(L, x) - p(K, x)| &\leq \sqrt{4d\delta + \delta^2} \leq \sqrt{5D\delta} \\ \text{Since } d < D \text{ and } \delta < D & \end{aligned}$$

□

From this proposition we can see that the metric projection is continuous in both variables. We will use this proposition in proving the weakly continuous property, which is theorem 2.4.1.

2.4 Measure space on Convex bodies

Definition 2.4.1. For a convex body $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$ and a real number $\rho \geq 0$ the outer parallel body of K at distance ρ is the set

$$K_\rho := K + \rho B^3 = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid d(K, x) \leq \rho\}$$

Lemma 2.4.1. Let $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$ and $\rho > 0$. The map $f_\rho : K_\rho \setminus K \rightarrow \Sigma$ as

$$x \mapsto (p(K, x), u(K, x))$$

where $p(K, \cdot)$ is the metric projection map for K and $u(K, \cdot)$ is outer normal vector map is measurable.

Proof. Theorem 2.3.1 states that the metric projection is contracting, which means

$$|p(A, x) - p(A, y)| \leq |x - y| \text{ for } x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

For a given $\epsilon > 0$, then $|p(A, x) - p(A, y)| \leq |x - y| < \epsilon$ whenever $|x - y| < \delta = \epsilon$. Hence the metric projection map $p(K, \cdot)$ is continuous.

$$u(K, x) = \frac{x - p(K, x)}{|x - p(K, x)|}$$

as $x \notin K$ $|x - p(K, x)| \neq 0$. Since u is rational function of continuous functions, $u(K, \cdot)$ is continuous. Hence $(p(K, \cdot), u(K, \cdot))$ is jointly continuous. Thus we conclude f_ρ is continuous. As all continuous maps are measurable, f_ρ is measurable. \square

Remark 2. We observe that $f_\rho^{-1}(\eta) \subset K_\rho \setminus K \subset \mathbb{R}^3$, $\forall \eta \in \Sigma$

Definition 2.4.2. The image measure $\mu_\rho(K, \cdot)$ is defined as

$$\mu_\rho(K, \eta) = \mathcal{L}^3(f_\rho^{-1}(\eta))$$

where $\eta \in \mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$, which is the Borel Algebra of Σ .

Proposition 2.4.1. $\mu_\rho(K, \cdot)$ is a finite measure on $\mathcal{B}(\eta)$

Proof. $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$. By the Heine-Borel Theorem K is closed and bounded. By virtue of it's closeness K is measurable. As K is bounded we can find a cube Q of finite side-length that contains K . Since $K \subset Q$, we have $K_\rho \subset Q_\rho$. Thus K_ρ is measurable and has finite measure. As in the proof of Lemma 2.4.1,

f_ρ is continuous. Thus $f_\rho^{-1}(\eta)$ is open for any open $\eta \in \Sigma$. Open sets are measurable and $f_\rho^{-1}(\eta) \subset K_\rho \setminus K$ is bounded. Thus $\mathcal{L}^3(f_\rho^{-1}(K, \eta))$ is finite. Hence $\mu_\rho(K, \eta)$ is finite for all $\eta \in \Sigma$. \square

Definition 2.4.3. Let $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$ and $\rho > 0$. The local parallel set is defined as

$$M_\rho(K, \eta) = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid 0 < d(K, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } (p(K, x), u(K, x)) \in \eta\}$$

Theorem 2.4.1. Let $\{K_j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence in \mathcal{K}^3 with $K_j \rightarrow K$ for $j \rightarrow \infty$ under the metric defined in section 2.2 definition 2.2.1 Hausdorff distance. Then $\mu_\rho(K_j, \cdot) \rightarrow \mu_\rho(K, \cdot)$ for $j \rightarrow \infty$

Proof. Let $\eta \subset \Sigma$ be open, and let $x \in M_\rho(K, \eta)$ be a point with $d(K, x) < \rho$. By theorem metric projection 2.3.1 metric projection is continuous. Hence the distance map $|x - p(K, x)|$ and $u(K, x) = x - p(K, x)/|x - p(K, x)|$ is continuous as $x \in M_\rho(K, \eta) \subset K_\rho \setminus K$, $x \notin K$ and hence $|x - p(K, x)| \neq 0$. Metric projection is continuous in both variables by Proposition 2.3.1. Thus for a given $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$

$$d(K_j, x) \rightarrow d(K, x) \text{ and } (p(K_j, x), u(K_j, x)) \rightarrow (p(K, x), u(K, x)) \text{ for } j \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence for almost all j we have

$$d(K_j, x) < \rho \text{ and } (p(K_j, x), u(K_j, x)) \in \eta$$

. From here we can see that $M_\rho(K, \eta) \setminus \text{bd } K_\rho \subset \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} \bigcap_{i=1}^n M_\rho(K_i, \eta)$. This shows that

$$M_\rho(K, \eta) \setminus \text{bd } K_\rho \subset \liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} M_\rho(K_j, \eta)$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_\rho(K, \eta) &= \mu(M_\rho(K, \eta) \setminus \text{bd } K_\rho) \\ &\leq \mu(\liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} M_\rho(K_j, \eta)) \\ &\leq \liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} \mu(M_\rho(K_j, \eta)) \\ &= \liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} \mu_\rho(K_j, \eta) \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$m u_\rho(K, \eta) \leq \liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} \mu_\rho(K_j, \eta) \text{ for } \eta \in \Sigma \text{ open.} \quad (2.1)$$

Further, we have

$$\mu_\rho(K, \Sigma) = \mathcal{L}^3(K_\rho \setminus K) = \text{mathcal{H}}^3(K_\rho) - \mathcal{L}^3(K)$$

For any sequence of sets $(A_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ the lim sup is defined as

$$\limsup A_n = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} \bigcup_{i=1}^n A_i = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} B_n.$$

Since B_n are decreasing, if we assume the measure is finite we have

$$\mu(\limsup A_n) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(B_n) = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(B_n)$$

where μ is the measure. But $A_n \subset B_n$, so $\mu(A_n) \leq \mu(B_n)$, so the above implies

$$\mu(\limsup A_n) \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(A_n).$$

Similarly we may conclude

$$\mu(\liminf A_n) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(A_n).$$

If the limit of the sequence $A = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A_n$ exists, then by definition we know $A = \limsup A_n = \liminf A_n$. So by the previous inequalities

$$\liminf \mu(A_n) \geq \mu(A) \geq \limsup \mu(A_n).$$

Hence $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(A_n)$ exists and equals $\mu(A)$ and thus we have

$$\mathcal{L}^3((K_j)_\rho) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}^3(K_j)$$

and

$$\mathcal{L}^3(K_j) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}^3(K)$$

as $j \rightarrow \infty$. Thus

$$\mu_\rho(K_j, \Sigma) \rightarrow \mu_\rho(K, \Sigma) \text{ as } j \rightarrow \infty \quad (2.2)$$

From equation 2.1 and 2.2 by applying Theorem we conclude $\mu_\rho(K_j, \cdot) \xrightarrow{w} \mu_\rho(K, \cdot)$ \square

Theorem 2.4.2. For each $\eta \in \mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$ the function $\mu_\rho(\cdot, \eta): \mathcal{K}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is measurable

Proof. From Theorem 2.4.1 we know

$$\mu_\rho(K_j, \cdot) \xrightarrow{w} \mu_\rho(K, \cdot).$$

From theorem we obtain

$$\liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} \mu_\rho(K_j, \eta) \geq \mu_\rho(K, \eta)$$

for $\eta \in \Sigma$ open. Thus $\mu_\rho(\cdot, \eta)$ is lower semicontinuous. Let f be a lower semicontinuous function. Then $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} f(x) \geq f(x_0)$ where x_0 belongs to the domain of f . This implies that $\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0^+} (\inf_{0 < |x - x_0| < \delta} f(x)) \geq f(x_0)$. Thus there exists some $\delta > 0$ such that $\inf_{0 < |x - x_0| < \delta} f(x) \geq f(x_0)$ which implies $f(x) \geq f(x_0)$ for all $x \in \{z \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid 0 < |z - x_0| < \delta\}$. Hence for every $y < f(x_0)$ there exists a neighbourhood U of x such that

$$y < f(x) \text{ for all } x \in U \quad (2.3)$$

Consider $A = \{x \in X \mid f(x) > y\}$ where X is the domain of f . By equation 2.3, A is open. Since $A = f^{-1}\{(y, \infty)\}$ is open, f is measurable. Thus $\mu_\rho(K, \eta)$ is measurable. Now we will show that the assertion given in the theorem statement is true. Let D be the family of all sets $\eta \in \mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$ for which $\mu_\rho(\cdot, \eta)$ is measurable. Then $D \subset \mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$ by definition of D . We will show that D contains $\mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$. $\mu_\rho(K, \Sigma) = \mu(f_\rho^{-1}(\Sigma)) = \mu(K_\rho \setminus K)$. We know $K_\rho \setminus K$ is measurable. Hence

$$\Sigma \in D \quad (2.4)$$

For $\eta_1, \eta_2 \in D$ with $\eta_1 \subset \eta_2$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} M_\rho(K, \eta_1) &\subset M_\rho(K, \eta_2) \\ x \in M_\rho(K, \eta_1) &\Rightarrow 0 < d(K, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } (p(K, x), u(k, x)) \in \eta_1 \\ &\Rightarrow 0 < d(K, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } (p(K, x), u(k, x)) \in \eta_2 \because \eta_1 \subset \eta_2 \\ &\Rightarrow x \in M_\rho(K, \eta_2) \end{aligned}$$

also $M_\rho(K, \eta_1 \setminus \eta_2) = M_\rho(K, \eta_1) \setminus M_\rho(K, \eta_2)$

$$\begin{aligned} x \in M_\rho(K, \eta_1 \setminus \eta_2) &\Leftrightarrow 0 < d(K, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } (p(K, x), u(K, x)) \in \eta_1 \setminus \eta_2 \\ &\Leftrightarrow (0 < d(K, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } (p(K, x), u(K, x)) \in \eta_1) \text{ and } (0 < d(K, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } (p(K, x), u(K, x)) \in \eta_2^c) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x \in M_\rho(K, \eta_1) \text{ and } M_\rho(K, \eta_2^c)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x \in M_\rho(K, \eta_1 \setminus \eta_2)$$

$$\therefore \mu_\rho(K, \eta_1 \setminus \eta_2) = \mu_\rho(K, \eta_1) - \mu_\rho(K, \eta_2)$$

Hence

$$\eta_1 \setminus \eta_2 \in D \tag{2.5}$$

Thus from equation 2.4 and 2.5 we obtain

$$\eta \in D \Rightarrow \eta^c \in D \tag{2.6}$$

For $\eta_1, \eta_2, \dots, \eta_k \in D$, we have $M_\rho(K, \cup_{j=1}^k \eta_j) = \cup_{j=1}^k M_\rho(K, \eta_j)$

$$x \in M_\rho(K, \cup_{j=1}^k \eta_j)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow 0 < d(K, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } x \in \cup_{j=1}^k \eta_j$$

$$\Leftrightarrow 0 < d(K, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } x \in \eta_1 \text{ or } \dots \text{ or } 0 < d(K, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } x \in \eta_k$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x \in M_\rho(K, \eta_1) \text{ or } \dots \text{ or } x \in M_\rho(K, \eta_k)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x \in \cup_{j=1}^k M_\rho(K, \eta_j)$$

We know that the finite union of Lebesgue measurable sets is Lebesgue measurable. Hence $\cup_{j=1}^k \eta_j \in D$. For any pairwise disjoint countable collection of sets $\{\eta_j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$,

$$\mu_\rho(K, \cup_{j=1}^\infty \eta_j) = \sum_{j=1}^\infty \mu_\rho(K, \eta_j)$$

for $K \in \mathcal{K}^n$ since $\mu_\rho(K, \cdot)$ is a measure. Hence $\cup_{j=1}^\infty \eta_j \in D$. Any countable union of sets in D can be represented as a union of pairwise disjoint sets

$$\{\{\eta_j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}, \rho_j = \eta_j \setminus \cup_{k=1}^{j-1} \eta_k\}$$

Hence for any countable collection $\{\eta_j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ in D we have

$$\cup_{j=1}^\infty \eta_j \in D \tag{2.7}$$

From equation (2.4), (2.6) and (2.7) we conclude that D is a σ -algebra. Now D contains the open sets of Σ . Hence D contains the σ -algebra generated by the open sets of Σ . Hence $\mathcal{B}(\Sigma) \subset D$. Hence $D = \mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$ \square

Theorem 2.4.3. For each $\eta \in \mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$, the function $\mu_\rho(\cdot, \eta)$ is additive, that is

$$\mu_\rho(K_1 \cup K_2, \eta) + \mu_\rho(K_1 \cap K_2, \eta) = \mu_\rho(K_1, \eta) + \mu_\rho(K_2, \eta)$$

Proof. Let $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be given and suppose that $y := p(K_1 \cup K_2, x) \in K_1$, without loss of generality. Thus $|y - x| \leq |x - x_1|$ for all $x_1 \in K_1$. By definition of metric projection, $p(K_1 \cup K_2, x) = p(K_1, x)$. Let $p(K_2, x) =: z$. Since $K_1 \cup K_2$ is convex, there is a point $a \in [z, y]$ for which $a \in K_1 \cap K_2$. (If not, we have found 2 points $z, y \in K_1 \cup K_2$ such that $[z, y] \not\subset K_1 \cup K_2$, contradicting the fact that $K_1 \cup K_2$ is convex).

Since $y = p(K_1 \cup K_2, x)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |y - x| &\leq |z - x| \\ \Rightarrow \lambda|z - x| + (1 - \lambda)|y - x| &\leq \lambda|z - x| + (1 - \lambda)|z - x| \end{aligned}$$

By Triangle Inequality, $\lambda|z - x| + (1 - \lambda)|y - x| \geq |\lambda z + (1 - \lambda)y - x|$

$$\text{Hence, } |\lambda z + (1 - \lambda)y - x| \leq |z - x|$$

$$\Rightarrow |a - x| \leq |z - x|$$

Strict inequality is impossible, as it will violate the definition of metric projection. Thus $a = z$, and hence $z \in K_1 \cap K_2$. It follows that

$$p(K_2, x) = p(K_1 \cap K_2, x). \quad (2.8)$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} x - p(K_1 \cup K_2, x) &= x - p(K_1, x) \\ x - p(K_1 \cap K_2, x) &= x - p(K_2, x) \\ \Rightarrow |x - p(K_1 \cup K_2, x)| &= |x - p(K_1, x)| \\ |x - p(K_1 \cap K_2, x)| &= |x - p(K_2, x)| \\ \Rightarrow d(K_1 \cap K_2) &= d(K_2, x) \\ d(K_1 \cup K_2) &= d(K_1, x) \\ \Rightarrow u(K_1 \cap K_2) &= u(K_2, x) \\ u(K_1 \cup K_2) &= u(K_1, x) \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < d(K_1, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } (p(K_1, x), u(K_1, x)) &\in \eta \\ \Rightarrow 0 < d(K_1 \cup K_2, x) \leq \rho \text{ and } (p(K_1 \cup K_2, x), u(K_1 \cup K_2, x)) &\in \eta \\ \Rightarrow M_\rho(K_1, \eta) = M_\rho(K_1 \cup K_2, x) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly from equation 2.8, we have $M_\rho(K_2, \eta) = M_\rho(K_1 \cap K_2, x)$ Let $I_\rho(K, \eta, \cdot)$ denote the characteristic function of $M_\rho(K, \eta)$

$$\Rightarrow I_\rho(K_1 \cap K_2, \eta, x) = I_\rho(K_2, \eta, x)$$

$$I_\rho(K_1 \cup K_2, \eta, x) = I_\rho(K_1, \eta, x)$$

$$\Rightarrow I_\rho(K_1 \cup K_2, \eta, x) + I_\rho(K_1 \cap K_2, \eta, x) = I_\rho(K_1, \eta, x) + I_\rho(K_2, \eta, x)$$

As x was arbitrarily chosen we have

$$I_\rho(K_1 \cup K_2, \eta, \cdot) + I_\rho(K_1 \cap K_2, \eta, \cdot) = I_\rho(K_1, \eta, \cdot) + I_\rho(K_2, \eta, \cdot)$$

Integration of the above equality yields the assertion □

Remark 3. We needed this theorem to show that μ_ρ is additive to conclude that $(\mathcal{K}^3 \times \mathcal{B}(\Sigma), \mu_\rho)$ is a measure space.

Chapter 3

Steiner Formula

3.1 Topology on Convex Bodies

In this chapter we finally tackle the Steiner Formula for general convex bodies. To do so we start off with some more general properties of convex bodies and concepts of relative interior and relative boundary, which are interior and boundary but restricted to a lower dimension. We state about convex functions and define support and separation of convex bodies in terms of planes. Then we state results which help us in establishing a representation of convex bodies in terms of its extreme points and extreme rays, which are forms of faces of the convex bodies. We define a face of convex bodies and define results which state the representation of the boundary of convex bodies in terms of the faces. Then we define polytopes which are special kinds of convex bodies and establish certain results for them. All these results will help us in proving the existence of curvature measures and surface area measures for the polytopes. This lays the background for proving the Steiner formula for polytopes and ultimately for general convex bodies the formula is established.

Theorem 3.1.1. *Caratheodory's Theorem*

If $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $x \in \text{conv } A$, then x is a convex combination of affinely independent points of A . In particular, x is a convex combination of $n + 1$ or fewer points of A .

Proof. $x \in \text{conv } A$. By definition of $\text{conv } A$ x is a convex combination of

finitely many points in A . Hence we may find $k \in \mathbb{N}$ minimal such that

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i x_i \text{ with } x \in A, \lambda_i > 0, \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i = 1,$$

Assume x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k are affinely dependent. Then there are numbers

$$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k \in \mathbb{R},$$

not all zero, such that

$$\sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i x_i = 0 \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i = 0.$$

If α_i are negative, then $\sum \alpha_i < 0$ which is not possible. Hence at least 1 α_i is positive. Thus we may choose m such that $\lambda_m/\alpha_m > 0$ and λ_m/α_m is minimum. This choice can be done since there are finitely many choices such that $\lambda_i/\alpha_i > 0$. Thus we have

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^k (\lambda_i - (\lambda_m/\alpha_m)\alpha_i)x_i,$$

all coefficients are non-negative by choice of m and at least one of them is zero. This contradicts the minimality of k . Thus x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k are affinely independent.

We know that a finite collection of points $y_0, y_1, \dots, y_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are affinely dependent if $y_1 - y_0, y_2 - y_0, \dots, y_k - y_0$ are linearly independent. In \mathbb{R}^3 at most 3 points may be linearly independent. Thus $k \leq 4$. □

Definition 3.1.1. The relative interior of set S is defined as the interior within it's affine hull. In other words

$$\text{relint } S := \{x \in S \mid \exists \epsilon > 0, N_\epsilon(x) \cap \text{aff } S \neq \emptyset\}$$

where $N_\epsilon(x)$ is the ϵ -neighbourhood of x and $\text{aff}(S)$ is the affine hull of S

Definition 3.1.2. The relative boundary of a set S is defined as the boundary of the affine hull of S . In other words,

$$\text{rel bd } S := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \forall N_\epsilon(x) \cap \text{aff } S \in x (N_\epsilon(x) \cap \text{aff } S) \cap S \neq \emptyset, (N_\epsilon(x) \cap \text{aff } S) \cap S^c \neq \emptyset\}$$

Figure 3.1: The shaded area is the relative interior of the disc

Theorem 3.1.2. *Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be convex. Then*

- (a) $\text{relint } A = \text{relint } \text{cl } A$
- (b) $\text{cl } A = \text{cl } \text{relint } A$
- (c) $\text{relbd } A = \text{relbd } A = \text{relbd } \text{relint } A$

Proof. We may assume that $\dim A = n$.

- Trivially, $\text{int } A \subset \text{int } \text{cl } A$. Let $x \in \text{int } \text{cl } A$. As A is convex, $\text{cl } A$ is convex. This is due to Lemma 1.1.1, as given any $x_1 \in \text{int } A$ and $y_1 \in \text{cl } A$ we have $[x_1, y_1) \subset \text{int } A$, hence $[x_1, y_1] \in \text{cl } A$. For $x \in \text{int } \text{cl } A$ there exists $y \in \text{int } A$ and $z \in \text{cl } A$ such that $x \in [y, z)$, because if not then it violates the fact that $\text{cl } A$ is convex. By Lemma 1.1.1 we conclude that $x \in \text{int } A$.
- Trivially, $\text{cl } A \subset \text{cl } \text{int } A$. Let $x \in \text{cl } A$. For any $y \in \text{int } A$ $[y, x) \subset \text{int } A$ by Lemma 1.1.1. Thus for any neighbourhood $N(x, |y - x|)$ we may find a point in $\text{int } A$ and a point outside of $\text{int } A$. Hence $x \in \text{cl } \text{int } A$. Thus $\text{cl } A \subset \text{cl } \text{int } A$.
- $\text{bd } \text{cl } A = \text{cl } (\text{cl } A) \setminus \text{int } (\text{cl } A) = \text{cl } A \setminus \text{int } A = \text{bd } A$ by (a). Then $\text{bd } \text{int } A = \text{cl } (\text{int } A) \setminus \text{int } (\text{int } A) = \text{cl } A \setminus \text{int } A = \text{bd } A$ using (b).

□

Definition 3.1.3. A function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty, -\infty\}$ is called convex if the function is proper, which means that $\{f = -\infty\} = \emptyset$ and $\{f = \infty\} \neq \mathbb{R}^n$, and if

$$f((1-\lambda)x - \lambda y) \leq (1-\lambda)f(x) - \lambda f(y),$$

$\forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$.

Example: $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of the form $f(x) = \langle x, u \rangle + \alpha$ where $u \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$

Definition 3.1.4. The effective domain of a convex function f is defined as follows

$$\text{dom } f := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid f(x) < \infty\}.$$

Definition 3.1.5. Let $K \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a closed convex set and $\emptyset \neq K \neq \mathbb{R}^n$. Then the support function $h(K, \cdot) = h_K$ of K is defined as

$$h(K, u) := \sup_{x \in K} \langle x, u \rangle \quad \text{for } u \in \mathbb{R}^n$$

Example : $h(K, u) = |u|$ where K is a ball with radius 1.

Definition 3.1.6. For $u \in \text{dom } h(K, \cdot) \setminus \{0\}$ we define

$$\begin{aligned} H(K, u) &:= \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \langle x, u \rangle = h(K, u)\} \\ H^-(K, u) &:= \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \langle x, u \rangle \leq h(K, u)\} \\ F(K, u) &:= H(K, u) \cap K \end{aligned}$$

$H(K, u)$, $H^-(K, u)$ and $F(K, u)$ are, respectively the supporting hyperplane, supporting halfspace and support set of K with outer normal vector u .

Lemma 3.1.1. Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be nonempty, convex and closed and let $x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus A$. The hyperplane H through $p(A, x)$ orthogonal to $u(A, x)$ supports A

Proof. Let $z \in A$. Put $v := z - p(A, x)$. We define a function f as $f(t) = |x - (p(A, x) + tv)|^2$. f has a minimum at $t = 0$ by definition of metric projection. Hence $f'(0) \geq 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} f(t) &= |x - (p(A, x) + tv)|^2 \\ &= \langle x - (p(A, x) + tv), x - (p(A, x) + tv) \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3.2: For a sphere, P supports it at A , the space below P is the supporting halfspace, and the support of the sphere is the singleton set containing the point A

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \langle (x - p(A, x)) - tv, (x - p(A, x)) - tv \rangle \\
 &= \langle x - p(A, x), x - p(A, x) \rangle - 2t \langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle + t^2 \langle v, v \rangle \\
 \Rightarrow f'(t) &= -2 \langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle + 2t \langle v, v \rangle \\
 \Rightarrow f'(0) &= -2 \langle x - p(A, x), v \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

This implies $\langle x - p(A, x), z - p(A, x) \rangle \leq 0$. As z was arbitrarily chosen,

$$\langle x - p(A, x), z - p(A, x) \rangle \leq 0$$

for all $z \in A$. As $u(A, x)$ is parallel to $x - p(A, x)$, we have

$$\langle z - p(A, x), u(A, x) \rangle \leq 0$$

for all $z \in A$. Thus A is contained in the closed halfspace

$$H^- = \{z \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \langle z - p(A, x), u(A, x) \rangle \leq 0\}.$$

Hence the hyperplane

$$H = \{z \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \langle z - p(A, x), u(A, x) \rangle = 0\}$$

supports A since $p(A, x) \in H \cap A$ and $A \subset H^-$. □

Definition 3.1.7. (Support and Separation)

Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $H \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a hyperplane and H^+, H^- be the closed half-spaces bounded by H . We say H supports A at x if $x \in A \cap H$ and either $A \subset H^+$ or $A \subset H^-$. Further, H is a support plane of A or supports A if H supports A at some x , which is necessarily a boundary point A . If $H = H_{u,\alpha} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \langle x, u \rangle = \alpha\}$ supports A and $A \subset H_{u,\alpha}^- = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \langle x, u \rangle \leq \alpha\}$ then $H_{u,\alpha}^-$ is called the supporting halfspace of A and u is called the exterior normal vector of both $H_{u,\alpha}^-$ and $H_{u,\alpha}$. If, moreover, $H_{u,\alpha}$ supports A at x , then u is an outer normal vector of A at x .

Let $A, B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be sets and $H_{u,\alpha} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ a hyperplane. The hyperplane $H_{u,\alpha}$ separates A and B if $A \subset H_{u,\alpha}^-$ and $B \subset H_{u,\alpha}^+$ or vice versa. This separation is said to be proper if A, B both do not lie in $H_{u,\alpha}$. The sets A and B are strictly separated by $H_{u,\alpha}$ if $A \subset \text{int } H_{u,\alpha}^-$ and $B \subset \text{int } H_{u,\alpha}^+$, or conversely, and they are strongly separated by $H^{u,\alpha}$ if there is a number ϵ such that $H^{u,\alpha-\epsilon}$ and $H^{u,\alpha+\epsilon}$ both separate A and B .

Theorem 3.1.3. (Support Theorem)

Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be convex and closed. Then through each boundary point of A there is a support plane of A . If $A \neq \emptyset$ is bounded, then to each vector $u \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{o\}$ there is a support plane to A with outer normal vector u .

Proof. Let $x \in \text{bd } A$. First let A be bounded. By Lemma 1.3.1 there is a point $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus A$ such that $x = p(A, y)$. By Lemma 1.4.1 the hyperplane through $p(A, y) = x$ orthogonal to $y - x$ supports A .

If A is unbounded, there exists a support plane H to $A \cap B(x, 1)$ through x ; let H^- be the corresponding supporting halfspace of $A \cap B(x, 1)$. If there is a point $z \in A \setminus H^-$, then $[z, x] \subset A$, but $[z, x] \cap B(x, 1) \not\subset H^-$, a contradiction. Hence H supports A .

Let A be bounded and $u \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{o\}$. Since A is compact, there is a point $x \in A$ satisfying $\langle x, u \rangle = \max\{\langle y, u \rangle : y \in A\}$. Define $H := \{y \in \mathbb{R}^n : \langle y, u \rangle = \langle x, u \rangle\}$. Then $A \subset H^- = \{y \in \mathbb{R}^n : \langle y, u \rangle \leq \langle x, u \rangle\}$ and x is a boundary point of A . Thus H supports A . □

Theorem 3.1.4. Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be convex and let $x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus A$. Then A and x can be separated. If A is closed, then A and x can be strongly separated.

Proof. If A is closed, the hyperplane through $p(A, x)$ orthogonal to $u(A, x)$ supports A . Thus $A \subset H^-$ and $x \in H^+$ and hence separates A and x . Consider

the hyperplane H_1 through $(p(A, x) + x)/2$ orthogonal to $u(A, x)$. Denote H_1 as $H_1 = H_{u(A, x), \langle u(A, x), (p(A, x) + x)/2 \rangle}$ and ϵ as $\langle u(A, x), (p(A, x) + x)/2 \rangle$. Then

$$H_{u(A, x), \langle u(A, x), (p(A, x) + x)/2 \rangle + \epsilon} = H_2$$

and

$$H_{u(A, x), \langle u(A, x), (p(A, x) + x)/2 \rangle - \epsilon} = H_3$$

separates A and x , since $H^- \subset H_3^-$ and $x \in H_3 \subset H_3^-$ and $H_2 = H$. Thus H_1 strongly separates A and x . If A is not closed and $x \notin \text{cl } A$, then the support plane H through $p(A, x)$ orthogonal to $u(A, x)$ separates $\text{cl } A$ and x by our discussion above. $A \subset \text{cl } A \subset H^-$ and $x \in H^+$. Thus this hyperplane also separates A and x . \square

Definition 3.1.8. A flat or a Euclidean subspace is a subset of a Euclidean space which is itself a Euclidean space (of lower dimension). The flats in 2-dimensional space are points and lines, and the flats in 3-dimensional space are points lines and planes. In n -dimensional space, there are flats of dimension from 0 to $n - 1$. The $n - 1$ -dimensional subspace are called hyperplanes.

The intersection of a flat with a closed halfspace is called a half-flat.

Lemma 3.1.2. If $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is a closed convex set with $A \neq \text{conv rel bd } A$, then A is either a flat or half-flat

Proof. We may assume $\dim A = n$, since if $\dim A \leq n$ then we are done by the definition of flats and half-flats. Since A is closed and convex, $\text{conv bd } A \subset A$. We assume $A \neq \text{conv bd } A$. Thus there exists a point $x \in \text{int } A$ such that $x \notin \text{conv bd } A$, since otherwise $\text{int } A \cap \text{bd } A \subset \text{conv bd } A$, and thus we would have $\text{int } A \cap \text{bd } A = \text{conv bd } A$ which would lead us to concluding $A = \text{conv bd } A$ (since A is closed) which would be a contradiction to our assumption. By Separation Theorem there is a closed halfspace H^- such that $x \in H^-$ and $\text{conv bd } A \subset H^+$. As $\text{bd } A \subset H^+$ since $\text{bd } A \subset \text{conv bd } A$, we have $[x, y] \cap \text{bd } A = \emptyset$ for each point $y \in \text{int } H^-$, thus $y \in \text{int } A$ since if not $[x, y] \cap \text{bd } A \neq \emptyset$. Thus $\text{int } H^- \subset \text{int } A$. Thus $\text{cl int } H^- \subset \text{cl } A$. By Lemma 1.1.1 we have $H^- \subset A$.

Assume $A \neq \mathbb{R}^n$. Let $a \in \text{bd } A$ such that $d(H^-, a) = \max_{y \in A} d(H^-, y)$. Such a point exists since $A \neq \mathbb{R}^n$ and A is closed. Then there exist a point $b \in \text{bd } A$ such that $d(H^-, b) \leq d(H^-, a)$. Then we can find on $R(H^-, b)$ a point $c \notin A$ and a point $z \in H$ such that $x \in [a, z]$. As $H^- \subset A$, thus we can find 2 points

in A such that the line segment between them is not contained in A , which is a contradiction to the fact that A is convex. Hence $d(H^-, a) = d(H^-, b)$ for any $a, b \in \text{bd } A$. Thus we conclude $A = H^- + d$ for some $d \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Hence A is a halfspace

□

Definition 3.1.9. Let K be a convex set. If a singleton set $\{x\}$ is a face of K then it is called an extreme point. The set of extreme points of K is denoted as $\text{ext } K$. If a ray is a face of K then its called an extreme ray of K . The set of extreme rays of K is denoted as $\text{extr } K$.

Theorem 3.1.5. Every line-free closed convex set $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is the convex hull of its extreme points and extreme rays

$$A = \text{conv}(\text{ext } A \cup \text{extr } A)$$

Proof. If A is a point, there is nothing to prove. If $A = [a, b]$ for some $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^3$, then we know $[a, b] = \{a + \lambda(b - a), 0 \leq \lambda \leq 1\} = \{\lambda b + (1 - \lambda)a, 0 \leq \lambda \leq 1\}$. Hence the statement holds for $n \leq 1$. Suppose that $n \geq 2$, $\dim A = n$ (without loss of generality) and the assertion has been proved for convex sets of smaller dimension. By Lemma 2.3.1 we have $A = \text{conv } \text{bd } A$. By the Support Theorem, each point $x \in \text{bd } A$ lies in some support plane H of A . By the induction hypothesis, x lies in the convex hull of the extreme points and extreme rays of $H \cap A$. By the definition of face the extreme points and extreme rays of $H \cap A$ are extreme points and extreme rays of A . Thus

$$\begin{aligned} x &\in \text{conv}(\text{ext } A \cup \text{extr } A) \\ \Rightarrow \text{bd } A &\subset \text{conv}(\text{ext } A \cup \text{extr } A) \\ \Rightarrow \text{conv } \text{bd } A &\subset \text{conv}(\text{ext } A \cup \text{extr } A) \\ \Rightarrow A &\subset \text{conv}(\text{ext } A \cup \text{extr } A) \end{aligned}$$

All extreme points and extreme rays are contained in A since all faces are subsets of A . Since A is convex,

$$\text{conv}(\text{ext } A \cup \text{extr } A) \subset A.$$

Thus we conclude

$$\text{conv}(\text{ext } A \cup \text{extr } A) = A$$

□

Figure 3.3: For a cuboid as shown in figure the shaded areas are faces

Corollary 3.1.5.1. Minkowski's Theorem

Every convex body $K \in \mathcal{K}^n$ is the convex hull of its extreme points.

Proof. Let K be a convex body. Then K is compact. By Heine-Borel Theorem K is bounded. Hence K is line-free and $\text{extr } A = \emptyset$ since rays and lines are unbounded and a bounded set cannot contain an unbounded set. As K is line-free, by Theorem 1.4.1 $K = \text{conv ext } A$. \square

In this section we give the definition of a face of a convex body and some results concerning them.

Definition 3.1.10. Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ be a convex set. A face of A is a convex subset such that each segment $[x, y] \subset A$ with $F \cap \text{relint}[x, y] \neq \emptyset$ is contained in F . The definition of face can also be written as such : F is a face of K if every segment $[x, y] \subset K$ satisfying $\text{relint}[x, y] \cap F = \emptyset$ are not contained in F .

An i -dimensional face of convex set K is referred to as an i -face. By $\mathcal{F}(K)$ we denote the set of all faces of K and by $\mathcal{F}_i(K)$ the set of all i -faces of K .

\emptyset and K are itself faces of K . For empty set any segment $[x, y] \subset K$ satisfies this. Hence we have \emptyset is a face of K . As for K , any segment contained in K will satisfy $\text{relint}[x, y] \cap K \neq \emptyset$ and thus it is a face of K

Conventionally, the empty face has dimension -1. Now we move on to certain useful results regarding faces.

Theorem 3.1.6. *If F_i is a face of K for $i \in I$ (an index set) then $\bigcap_{i \in I} F_i$ is a face of K . If F is a face of K and G is a face of F then G is a face of K .*

Proof. Let F_i be a face of K for $i \in I$. This implies that line segment $[x, y] \subset K$ which $F_i \cap \text{relint}[x, y] \neq \emptyset$ is contained in F_i . Let $[x, y] \subset K$ such that $\text{relint}[x, y] \cap (\bigcap_{i \in I} F_i) \neq \emptyset$. Then $\text{relint}[x, y] \cap F_i \neq \emptyset \forall i \in I$ thus $[x, y] \subset F_i \forall i \in I$. Hence $[x, y] \subset \bigcap_{i \in I} F_i$ and we can conclude that $\bigcap_{i \in I} F_i$ is a face of K .

Given F is a face of K and G is a face of F . Consider $[x, y] \subset K$ with

$$\text{relint}[x, y] \cap G \neq \emptyset.$$

Since $G \subset F$, we have $\text{relint}[x, y] \cap F \neq \emptyset$. Also F is a face of K which implies that $[x, y] \subset F$. Thus $[x, y] \subset F$ with $\text{relint}[x, y] \cap G \neq \emptyset$. Thus $[x, y] \subset G$ because G is a face of F . Hence G is a face of K . □

Theorem 3.1.7. *If $F_1, F_2 \in \mathcal{F}(K)$ are distinct faces, then $\text{relint}F_1 \cap \text{relint}F_2 = \emptyset$. To each nonempty relatively open convex subset A of K there is a unique face F such that $A \subset \text{relint}F$. The system*

$$\{\text{relint}F : F \in \mathcal{F}(K)\}$$

is a disjoint decomposition of K .

Proof. Assume that $F_1, F_2 \in \mathcal{F}(K)$, $F_1 \neq F_2$ and $z \in \text{relint}F_1 \cap \text{relint}F_2$. Since $F_1 \neq F_2$, there exists $x \in F_1$ such that $x \notin F_2$. Thus we have $x \in F_1 \setminus F_2$. We can choose $y \in F_1$ such that $z \in \text{relint}[x, y]$ (if this not true then the convexity of F_1 is contradicted). From $[x, y] \subset F_1 \subset K$, and $F_2 \in \mathcal{F}(K)$ we have $[x, y] \subset F_2$ which is a contradiction. Thus we conclude that $\text{relint}F_1 \cap \text{relint}F_2 = \emptyset$.

Let A be a relatively open subset of K . Let F be the intersection of all faces containing A . Then by Theorem 2.1.1, F is a face of K . Suppose there is some point $x \in A \setminus \text{relint}F$. Then there is a support plane H to F at x and $H \cap F \neq F$, as x is a relative boundary point of F . Since $x \in A \subset F$ and A is relatively open, it follows that $A \subset H$.

(Let $y \in A \setminus H$. WLOG $y \in H^+$. we can find $y' \in H^-$ such that $x \in [y, y']$. As H is the supporting plane of F we can find such y belonging to F . As F is

convex and $A \subset F$ we can find such $y \in A$. $y' \notin A$ since $A \subset F$. Thus for each relative neighbourhood of x we can find one point in A and one point not in A . Thus x is relative boundary point of which is a contradiction since A is relatively open.

Now $H \cap F$ is a face of F and hence a face of K . But then $F \subset H \cap F$ by definition of F which is a contradiction. Thus $A \subset \text{relint} F$. It follows from the first part F is unique.

The set A may be one pointed. Thus each point $x \in K$ is contained $\text{relint} F$ for some unique face $F \in \mathcal{F}(K)$. □

Support sets are also called exposed faces.

Theorem 3.1.8. *If F_i is an exposed face of K for $i \in I \neq \emptyset$, then either $\bigcap_{i \in I} F_i$ is an exposed face of K or is empty.*

Proof. Let $F := \bigcap_{i \in I} F_i$ and assume that $F \neq \emptyset$. After a translation, we may assume $o \in F$. For $i \in I$ there exists a vector $u_i \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{o\}$ such that $F_i \subset K \cap H_{u_i,0}^-$. We may assume that u_1, u_2, \dots, u_r are linearly independent and that any other u_i is linearly dependent on these vectors. Then $F = \bigcap_{i=1}^r F_i$. Let $u = \sum_{i=1}^r u_i$. Then $K \subset H_{u,0}^-$ and $o \in K \cap H_{u,0}$, hence $H_{u,0}$ supports K . For $x \in F$ we have $\langle x, u \rangle = 0$; thus $F \subset H_{u,0} \cap K$. For $y \in K \setminus F$, we have $\langle y, u_j \rangle < 0$ for some $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$, hence $\langle y, u \rangle < 0$ and thus $y \notin H_{u,0}$. This proves that $H_{u,0} \cap K = F$ and therefore F is an exposed face of K . □

Definition 3.1.11. Let $K \in \mathcal{K}_{(0)}^3$. The polar body of K is defined as

$$K^\circ = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \langle x, y \rangle \leq 1 \forall y \in K\}$$

Definition 3.1.12. For a subset $F \subset K$ where $K \in \mathcal{K}_{(0)}^3$ we define a conjugate face as

$$\widehat{F} := \{x \in K^\circ : \langle x, y \rangle = 1 \forall y \in F\}$$

Theorem 3.1.9. *Let $k \in \mathcal{K}_{(0)}^n$ and $\emptyset \neq K \subset k$. Then the following assertions are equivalent*

1. F lies in an exposed face of K
2. $\widehat{F} \neq \emptyset$
3. \widehat{F} is an exposed face of K

Proof. • First we show that 2 implies 3 and vice versa.

For $y \in \text{bd } K$, the hyperplane $\{x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid \langle x, y \rangle = 1\}$ supports K° ; hence $\hat{y} = F(K^\circ, y)$ is an exposed face of K° . For $y \in \text{int } K$, $\langle x, y \rangle < 1$ for all $x \in K^\circ$, hence $\hat{y} = \emptyset$. By definition

$$\hat{F} = \bigcap_{y \in F} \{x \in K^\circ : \langle x, y \rangle = 1\} = \bigcap_{y \in F} \hat{y}.$$

Thus \hat{F} is either an empty set or an exposed face of K°

• Now we show 1 implies 2 and vice versa.

Suppose that F lies in the exposed face $S := K \cap H_{u,1}$ where $K \subset H_{u,1}^-$.

Then $u \in \hat{F}$ and hence $\hat{F} \neq \emptyset$. Conversely, if $u \in \hat{F}$, then $u \in K^\circ$ and $\langle u, y \rangle = 1$ for all $y \in F$, hence F lies in an exposed face of K .

Thus 1, 2 and 3 are equivalent. \square

Definition 3.1.13. A polytope in \mathbb{R}^3 is the convex hull of a finite (possibly empty) subset of \mathbb{R}^n .

Figure 3.4 A polytope

If a polytope P is the convex hull of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k , then the extreme points of P are among these points; hence by Minkowski Theorem they are convex bodies.

Theorem 3.1.10. *Every polytope is the intersection of finitely many half-spaces*

Proof. Let P be a polytope. Since flats and half-flats can be represented as intersections of finitely many closed halfspaces, it suffices to assume $\dim P = n$. Let F_1, F_2, \dots, F_k be the facets of P ; then $F_i = H_i \cap P$ where H_i is a unique support plane of P . Let H_i^- be the closed halfspace bounded by H_i and containing P ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$). We assert that

$$P = H_1^- \cap H_2^- \cap \dots \cap H_k^-$$

The inclusion $P \subset H_1^- \cap H_2^- \cap \dots \cap H_k^-$ is trivial. Let $x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus P$. Let A be the union of affine hulls of x and any $n-1$ vertices of P . We can choose a point $y \in (\text{int}P) \setminus A$. There is a point $z \in \text{bd} P \cap [x, y]$ (If not, then $[x, y] \subset \text{int} P$ or $[x, y] \subset \text{ext} P$, which is not possible as $x \notin P$ and $y \in P$). By Theorem 2.1.2 z lies in some face of P . Suppose that $\dim F =: j \leq 1$. By Caratheodory's Theorem, z belongs to the convex hull of some $j+1 \leq 2$ vertices of P and hence to A . But then $y \in A$, a contradiction. This shows that F is a facet, hence $F = F_i$ for suitable $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$. From $y \in \text{int}P \subset \text{int}H_i^-$, we deduce $x \notin H_i^-$. This proves our assertion. □

Corollary 3.1.10.1. *if P is a polytope in \mathbb{R}^3 and u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k are its normal vectors, then*

$$P = \bigcap_{i=1}^k H_{u_i, h(P, u_i)}^-$$

In, particular, the numbers $h(P, u_1), h(P, u_2), \dots, h(P, u_k)$ determine P uniquely

Proof. If F_i is the facet of P with normal vector u_i , then $F_i = P \cap H_{u_i, h(P, u_i)}$. Hence by Theorem 2.2.2 we can conclude

$$P = \bigcap_{i=1}^k H_{u_i, h(P, u_i)}^-$$

As for a given facet the hyperplane is unique thus our assertion holds true. □

Lemma 3.1.3. *Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k \in \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus \{0\}$. If*

$$P := \bigcap_{i=1}^k H_{u_i, 1}^-$$

is bounded, then

$$P^\circ = \text{conv}\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k\}$$

Proof. We remark that $o \in \text{int } P$, hence it is well defined.

Let $Q := \text{conv}\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k\}$. For $x \in P$ we have $\langle x, u_i \rangle \leq 1$, hence $u_i \in P^\circ$. Thus $Q \subset P^\circ$.

Let $v \in \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus Q$. Then there is a hyperplane $H_{z,\alpha}$ strongly separating Q and v , and by an appropriate choice of signs we may assume that $\langle z, u_i \rangle < \alpha$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ and $\langle z, v \rangle > \alpha$. Since P is bounded, clearly $\text{pos}\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k\} = \mathbb{R}^n$ (otherwise the closed convex cone $\text{pos}\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k\}$ has a boundary point and hence a supporting hyperplane, necessarily through o , each outer normal vector of which is an element of P); hence there is a representation

$$o = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i u_i \text{ with } \lambda_i \geq 0 \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i > 0.$$

This yields $0 < \sum \lambda_i \alpha$ and thus $\alpha > 0$; WLOG $\alpha = 1$. But then $z \in P$, hence $v \notin P^\circ$. This proves the inequality $Q = P^\circ$. □

Theorem 3.1.11. *Each proper face of a polytope P is contained in a facet of P*

Proof. We may assume that $\dim P = 3$. By Theorem 2.2.2 we know P has a representation

$$P = \bigcap_{i=1}^k H_i^-$$

where H_i^- is a closed halfspace and $F_i := P \cap H_i$ is a facet of P . Since $\text{bd } P \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^k (P \cap H_i)$ (For sets A, B inside a metric space $\text{bd}(A \cap B) \subset \text{bd } A \cup \text{bd } B$), each boundary point of P is contained in some facet F_j .

Now let F be a proper face of P and choose $x \in \text{relint } F$. Then $x \in F_j = P \cap H_j$ for some $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$. (As F is a proper face it is contained in the boundary of P). Since $x \in \text{relint } F$ and H_j is a support plane of P , we deduce $F \subset H_j$, hence $F \subset F_j$. □

Lemma 3.1.4. Suppose that $K \in \mathcal{K}_{(0)}^3$ and let F be a nonempty convex subset of K . Then

$$N(K, F) = \text{pos } \hat{F} \cup \{o\}$$

Proof. Let $u \in N(K, F) \setminus \{o\}$. Then $H_{v,1}$ with $v = h(K, u)^{-1}u$ is a support plane of K satisfying $x \in K \cap H_{v,1}$, for some point $x \in \text{relint } F$. It follows that $F \subset H_{v,1}$; hence $\langle y, v \rangle \leq 1$ for $y \in K$ and $\langle y, v \rangle = 1$ for $y \in F$. This shows that $v \in \widehat{F}$ and hence $u \in \text{pos } \widehat{F}$. Thus $N(K, F) \subset \text{pos } \widehat{F} \cap \{0\}$.

Reversing this argument we conclude our assertion to be true. □

Theorem 3.1.12. *Let P be a polytope in \mathbb{R}^3 , let F_1, F_2, \dots, F_k be its facets and let u_i be the outer unit normal vector of $F_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, k)$. If F is a proper face of P , then*

$$N(P, F) = \text{pos} \{u_i : F \subset F_i\}$$

Proof. We may assume $o \in \text{int } P$. From Lemma 2.2.2 we know that $N(P, F) = \text{pos } \widehat{F}$. Writing $v_i = u_i/h(P, u_i)$, we have

$$P = \bigcap_{i=1}^k H_{v_i,1}^-$$

by Corollary 2.2.2.1, hence Lemma 2.2.1 yields

$$P^\circ = \text{conv} \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k\}.$$

The face \widehat{F} of P° is the convex hull of those v_i that it contains, and $\text{pos } \widehat{F}$ is the positive hull of these v_i and hence of the corresponding u_i . Now $v_i \in \widehat{F}$ is equivalent to $F \subset F_i$. □

Definition 3.1.14. Let K be a convex body with interior points and let $x \in \text{bd } K$. We say that x is a r -singular point of K if $\dim N(K, x) \geq 3 - r$.

Lemma 3.1.5. Let K be a closed convex set. Then $N(K, x) = p_K^{-1}(x) - x$

Proof. $p_K^{-1}(x) - x = \{y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus K : p(K, y) = x\}$ By Lemma 1.3.1, for any $y \in p_K^{-1}(x) - x$ the hyperplane through y and orthogonal to $\frac{y-x}{|y-x|}$ supports K . Hence $y \in N(K, x)$. Thus we conclude $p_K^{-1}(x) - x \subset N(K, x)$.

Let $y \in N(K, x)$. Then $x \in H(K, y)$. Now let $z = \frac{y}{|y|}$. Then $x \in H(K, z)$ as well since $\langle x, y \rangle = h(K, y)$ implies $\frac{1}{|y|} \langle x, y \rangle = \frac{1}{|y|} h(K, y)$ and hence $\langle x, z \rangle = h(K, z)$. We know

$$|x - a|^2 = |x|^2 + 1 - 2\langle x, a \rangle$$

for any $a \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with modulus 1. By definition of $h(K, \cdot)$, $|x - z|^2$ is minimum. Hence $p(K, z) = x$. Now z and y belong to the the same ray and hence $p(A, y) = x$, Thus $y \in p_K^{-1}(y) - x$. □

Theorem 3.1.13. *Let K be a convex set with interior points and $r \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. The set of r -singular points of K can be covered by countable many compact sets of finite r -dimensional Hausdorff measure.*

Proof. Let M_r denote the intersection of a fixed closed ball, containing K in its interior, with the union of all r -dimensional affine subspaces of \mathbb{R}^3 that are spanned by rational coordinates. Let x be an r -singular point of K . Then the translated cone

$$N(K, x) + x = p_K^{-1}(x)$$

is of at least dimension $3 - r$. Hence this set meets M_r by Lemma 1.2.2 since if it had dimension 0 which is a single point then it might not meet the ball. Hence $x \in p_K(M_r)$. As metric projection p_K is continuous we conclude the assertion follows. \square

Definition 3.1.15. For a subset $\beta \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ we define the set of all outer normal vectors of K at points of β , thus

$$\sigma(K, \beta) := \bigcup_{x \in K \cap \beta} N(K, x) \cap \mathbb{S}^2$$

Definition 3.1.16. Let $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$ and $u \in \mathbb{S}^2$. The vector u is called a regular normal vector if $\dim F(K, u) = 0$; otherwise u is called singular.

Theorem 3.1.14. *The set of singular unit normal vectors of a convex body $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$ has 2-dimensional Lebesgue measure zero.*

Proof. We may assume $\dim K = 0$ and $o \in \text{int } K$ since translation does not change the measure of set. Let u be a singular normal vector of K . Then $H(K, u)$ contains a segment of F as $\dim F(K, u) \neq 0$. The point $x := h(K, u)^{-1}u$ is a boundary point of K° , and $F \subset \hat{x}$. We know $N(K, F) = \text{pos } \hat{F} \cup \{o\}$ from where it follows $N(K^\circ, x) \supset F$, hence x is a boundary point of K° . Then u is contained in the image M of the set of singular boundary points of K° under the radial projection from $\text{bd } K^\circ$ to \mathbb{S}^2 . As this is a continuous map, it follows from Theorem 2.3.1 that M has 2-dimensional Lebesgue measure zero. \square

Theorem 3.1.15. *Let $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$ and let $\beta \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ be a Borel set. Then the spherical image $\sigma(K, \beta)$ of K at β is Lebesgue measurable on \mathbb{S}^2*

Proof. Let M be the family of all subsets $\beta \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ for which the set $\sigma(K, \beta)$ is Lebesgue measurable. First, let β be closed. Let $(u_j)_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence in $\sigma(K, \beta)$ for which $u_j \rightarrow u$ for $j \rightarrow \infty$. For $j \in \mathbb{N}$, we can choose $x_j \in K \cap \beta$ such that $u_j \in N(K, x_j)$. Since $K \cap \beta$ is compact, a subsequence of x_j converges to a point $x \in K \cap \beta$, and from $u_j \rightarrow u$ it follows $u \in N(K, x)$, hence $u \in \sigma(K, \beta)$. Thus $\sigma(K, \beta)$ is closed and thus $\beta \in M$. Let $\beta \in M$ and consider β^c . Suppose that $u \in \sigma(K, \beta) \cap \sigma(K, \beta^c)$. Then $F(K, u)$ contains point of both β and β^c . Hence u is a singular normal vector of K . From Theorem 3.1.15 we have

$$\mathcal{L}^2(\sigma(K, \beta) \cap \sigma(K, \beta^c)) = 0.$$

Hence, the set $\sigma(K, \beta^c)$ differs from the set $\mathbb{S}^{n-1} \setminus \sigma(K, \beta)$, which is Lebesgue measurable, by a set of measure 0. Thus it follows $\sigma(K, \beta^c)$ is Lebesgue measurable and thus $\beta^c \in M$. Finally, we can see that $\sigma(K, \cup_i \beta_i) = \cup_i \sigma(K, \beta_i)$ for any family (β_i) . Thus we conclude M is a σ -algebra containing all closed sets. Hence M contains all Borel subsets of \mathbb{R}^3 , which proves our assertion. \square

Definition 3.1.17. For a subset $\omega \subset \mathbb{S}^2$ we denote by $\tau(K, \omega)$ the set of all boundary points of K at which there exist a normal vector belonging to ω , thus

$$\tau(K, \omega) := \bigcup_{u \in \omega} F(K, u).$$

This is called the reverse spherical map of K at ω .

Theorem 3.1.16. Let $K \in \mathcal{K}_{(0)}^3$ and let $\omega \subset \mathbb{S}^2$ be a Borel set. Then $f(\tau(K, \omega))$ is Lebesgue measurable on \mathbb{S}^2 , where f is defined as $f : \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus \{o\} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^2$ by $f(x) = \frac{x}{|x|}$

Proof. Let M be the family of all subsets $\beta \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ for which the set $f(\tau(K, \omega))$ is Lebesgue measurable. First, let β be closed. Let $(u_j)_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence in $\tau(K, \omega)$ for which $u_j \rightarrow u$ for $j \rightarrow \infty$. For $j \in \mathbb{N}$, we can choose $x_j \in \omega$ such that $u_j \in F(K, x_j)$. Since ω is compact, a subsequence of x_j converges to a point $x \in \omega$, and from $u_j \rightarrow u$ it follows $u \in F(K, x)$, hence $u \in \tau(K, \beta)$. Thus $\sigma(K, \beta)$ is closed. Since f is a continuous map then $f(\tau(K, \omega))$ is closed and thus measurable. Hence $\omega \in M$. Let $\beta \in M$ and consider β^c . Suppose that $u \in f(\tau(K, \beta)) \cap f(\tau(K, \beta^c))$. Then $F(K, u)$ contains point of both β and β^c . Hence u is a singular boundary point of K . From Theorem 3.1.15 we have

$$\mathcal{L}^2(f(\tau(K, \beta)) \cap f(\tau(K, \beta^c))) = 0.$$

Hence, the set $f(\tau(K, \beta^c))$ differs from the set $\mathbb{S}^2 \setminus f(\tau(K, \beta))$, which is Lebesgue measurable, by a set of measure 0. Thus it follows $\tau(K, \beta^c)$ is Lebesgue measurable and thus $\beta^c \in M$. Finally, we can see that $f(\tau(K, \cup_i \beta_i)) = \cup_i f(\tau(K, \beta_i))$ for any family (β_i) . Thus we conclude M is a σ -algebra containing all closed sets. Hence M contains all Borel subsets of \mathbb{R}^3 , which proves our assertion. \square

3.2 Steiner Formula for Polytopes and General Convex Bodies

Let $P \in \mathcal{K}^3$ be a polytope. For $x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus P$ the nearest point $p(P, x)$ belongs to the the relative interior of a unique face of P by Theorem 3.1.7. By Lemma 3.1.5 we have

$$N(P, x) + x = p(P, \cdot)^{-1}(x)$$

for $x \in \text{relint } F$. By the definition of direct sum we have

$$p(P, \cdot)^{-1}(\text{relint } F) = \text{relint } F \oplus N(P, \text{relint } F).$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} p(P, \cdot)^{-1}(\text{relint } F) &= \text{relint } F \oplus N(P, \text{relint } F) \\ \Rightarrow (P_\rho \setminus P) \cap p(P, \cdot)^{-1}(\text{relint } F) &= \text{relint } F \oplus (N(P, \text{relint } F) \cap \rho B^3) \end{aligned}$$

As $\mathcal{L}^3(\text{rel bd } F) = 0$ by Lemma 1.0.3 which states $\dim \text{rel bd } F \leq 2$ and we conclude the truth of the statement by Lemma 1.0.2. Thus we have

$$\mathcal{L}^3((P_\rho \setminus P) \cap p(P, \cdot)^{-1}(\text{relint } F)) = \mathcal{L}^3(F \oplus (N(P, \text{relint } F) \cap \rho B^3))$$

where B^3 is the 3-dimensional ball of radius 1. We had defined $N(P, F)$ as $N(P, F) = N(P, x)$ for $x \in \text{relint } F$. Thus $N(P, \text{relint } F) = N(P, F)$. Thus we have

$$\mathcal{L}^3((P_\rho \setminus P) \cap p(P, \cdot)^{-1}(\text{relint } F)) = \mathcal{L}^3(F \oplus (N(P, F) \cap \rho B^3)).$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^3(M_\rho(P, \eta) \cap p(P, \cdot)^{-1}(\text{relint } F)) \\ = \mathcal{L}^3((F \cap \beta) \oplus (N(P, F) \cap \rho B^3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \int_F \mathcal{L}^{3-m} \{z \in N(P, F) : 0 < |z| \leq \rho, (y, z/|z|) \in \eta\} d\mathcal{L}^m(y) \\
 &= \int_F \mathcal{L}^{3-m} \{\lambda u : 0 < \lambda \leq \rho, u \in N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2(y, u) \in \eta\} d\mathcal{L}^m(y) \\
 &= \frac{\rho^{3-m}}{3-m} \int_F \int_{N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2} 1_\eta(y, u) d\mathcal{L}^{2-m}(u) d\mathcal{L}^m(y)
 \end{aligned}$$

From Theorem 3.1.7 we know that the following is a disjoint decomposition

$$\mathbb{R}^3 \setminus P = \bigcup_{m=0}^2 \bigcup_{F \in \mathcal{F}_m(P)} \{x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus P : p(P, x) \in \text{relint } F\}$$

As the above is a disjoint decomposition we can add the Lebesgue measure calculated above for each face and obtain

$$\mu_\rho(P, \eta) = \sum_{m=0}^2 \frac{\rho^{3-m}}{3-m} \sum_{F \in \mathcal{F}_m(P)} \int_F \int_{N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2} 1_\eta(y, u) d\mathcal{L}^{2-m}(u) d\mathcal{L}^m(y)$$

We define

$$\binom{2}{m} \Theta_m(P, \eta) := \sum_{F \in \mathcal{F}_m(P)} \int_F \int_{N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2} 1_\eta(y, u) d\mathcal{L}^{2-m}(u) d\mathcal{L}^m(y)$$

for $m = 0, 1, 2$, so that

$$\mu_\rho(P, \eta) = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{m=0}^2 \rho^{3-m} \binom{3}{m} \Theta_m(P, \eta) \quad (3.1)$$

Theorem 3.2.1. *For every convex body $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$ there exists finite positive measures $\Theta_0(K, \cdot), \Theta_1(K, \cdot), \Theta_2(K, \cdot)$ on $\mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$ and every $\rho > 0$, the measure $\mu_\rho(K, \eta)$ of the local parallel set $M_\rho(K, \eta)$ is given by*

$$\mu_\rho(K, \eta) = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{m=0}^2 \rho^{3-m} \binom{3}{m} \Theta_m(K, \eta) \quad (3.2)$$

The mapping $K \mapsto \Theta_m(K, \cdot)$ is weakly continuous and additive, that is,

$$K_j \longrightarrow K \Rightarrow \Theta_m(K_j, \cdot) \longrightarrow \Theta_m(K, \cdot)$$

and K_1, K_2 and $K_1 \cap K_2$ implies

$$\Theta_m(K_1 \cap K_2, \cdot) + \Theta_m(K_1 \cup K_2, \cdot) = \Theta_m(K_1, \cdot) + \Theta_m(K_2, \cdot)$$

For each $\eta \in \mathbb{B}(\Sigma)$, the function $\Theta_m(\cdot, \eta)$ is measurable.

Proof. Let P be a polytope. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_1(P, \eta) &= \frac{1}{3}\Theta_0(P, \eta) + \Theta_1(P, \eta) + \Theta_2(P, \eta) \\ \mu_2(P, \eta) &= \frac{8}{3}\Theta_0(P, \eta) + 4\Theta_1(P, \eta) + \Theta_2(P, \eta) \\ \mu_3(P, \eta) &= 9\Theta_0(P, \eta) + 3\Theta_1(P, \eta) + \Theta_2(P, \eta)\end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mu_1(P, \eta) \\ \mu_2(P, \eta) \\ \mu_3(P, \eta) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 3 & 3 \\ 8 & 12 & 6 \\ 27 & 9 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Theta_1(P, \eta) \\ \Theta_2(P, \eta) \\ \Theta_3(P, \eta) \end{bmatrix}$$

We get

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Theta_1(P, \eta) \\ \Theta_2(P, \eta) \\ \Theta_3(P, \eta) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{20} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & -3 & 3 \\ -23 & 13 & -3 \\ 42 & -12 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mu_1(P, \eta) \\ \mu_2(P, \eta) \\ \mu_3(P, \eta) \end{bmatrix}$$

This implies

$$\begin{aligned}\Theta_1(P, \eta) &= \frac{1}{20}(3\mu_1(P, \eta) - 3\mu_2(P, \eta) + 3\mu_3(P, \eta)) \\ \Theta_2(P, \eta) &= \frac{1}{20}(-23\mu_1(P, \eta) + 13\mu_2(P, \eta) - 3\mu_3(P, \eta)) \\ \Theta_3(P, \eta) &= \frac{1}{20}(42\mu_1(P, \eta) - 12\mu_2(P, \eta) + 2\mu_3(P, \eta))\end{aligned}$$

We have seen from our definition of Θ_i for polytopes that $\Theta_i(P, \eta) > 0$ for any polytope P and any $\eta \in \mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$. As concluded above Θ_i are linear combination of μ_i 's. Hence by Theorem 2.4.2 we have $\Theta_i(P_i, \cdot) \xrightarrow{w} \Theta_i(K, \cdot)$. Hence for a sequence of polytopes P_i converging to K . As convex bodies are a complete metric space we can find for each convex body K a sequence of polytopes converging to K . Hence Θ_m is a positive measure.

As μ_ρ is weakly continuous, additive and $\mu_\rho(\cdot, \eta)$ for each $\eta \in \mathcal{B}(\Sigma)$ by Theorem 2.4.2, 2.4.3, and 2.4.5, and Θ_i are linear combinations of μ_i , we can conclude that all assertions stated in the theorem statement are satisfied. \square

Definition 3.2.1. From the support measures $\Theta_m(K, \cdot)$, we can derive the marginal measures curvature measures and surface area measures as follows

$$C_m(K, \beta) := \Theta_m(K, \beta \times \mathbb{S}^2)$$

$$S_m(K, \omega) := \Theta_m(K, \mathbb{R}^3 \times \omega)$$

where $\beta \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^3)$, $\omega \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S}^2)$

Theorem 3.2.2. *Let $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$, $\beta \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^3)$, $\omega \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S}^2)$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} C_0(K, \beta) &= \mathcal{L}^2(\sigma(K, \beta)) \\ S_0(K, \omega) &= \mathcal{L}^2(\omega) \end{aligned}$$

If K is 3-dimensional then

$$\begin{aligned} C_2(K, \beta) &= \mathcal{L}^3(\beta \cap b dK) \\ S_2(K, \omega) &= \mathcal{L}^3(\tau(K, \omega)) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. First we will show that the results hold true for polytopes. We know

$$\binom{3}{m} \Theta_m(P, \eta) := \sum_{F \in \mathcal{F}_m(P)} \int_F \int_{N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2} 1_\eta(y, u) d\mathcal{L}^{2-m}(u) d\mathcal{L}^m(y).$$

Thus

$$\binom{2}{m} C_m(P, \beta) := \sum_{F \in \mathcal{F}_m(P)} \int_F \int_{N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2} 1_{\beta \times \mathbb{S}^2}(y, u) d\mathcal{L}^{2-m}(u) d\mathcal{L}^m(y).$$

Integrating we obtain

$$\binom{2}{m} C_m(P, \beta) := \sum_{F \in \mathcal{F}_m(P)} \mathcal{L}^{2-m}(N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2) \mathcal{L}^m(F \cap \beta)$$

. Similarly we have

$$\binom{2}{m} S_m(P, \omega) := \sum_{F \in \mathcal{F}_m(P)} \mathcal{L}^{2-m}(N(P, F) \cap \omega) \mathcal{L}^m(F)$$

. Thus for $m = 0$ and $m = 2$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} C_0(P, \beta) &= \sum_{x \in \beta \cap \text{ext } P} \mathcal{L}^2(N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2) \\ S_0(P, \omega) &= \sum_{x \in \text{ext } P} \mathcal{L}^2(N(P, x) \cap \omega) \end{aligned}$$

$$C_2(P, \beta) = \sum_{F \in \mathcal{F}_2(P)} \mathcal{L}^{n-1}(F \cap \beta)$$

$$S_2(P, \beta) = \sum_{u \in \omega} \mathcal{L}^2(F(K, u))$$

since every proper face of a polytope are exposed faces as well. We know that for faces F, G $F \subset G$ implies $N(P, F) \supset N(P, G)$; also $\dim N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2 \leq 1$. Hence $C_0(P, \beta) = \mathcal{L}^2(\cup_{x \in \beta \cap P} N(P, F) \cap \mathbb{S}^2) = \mathcal{L}^2(\sigma(K, \beta))$. We know $\cup_{x \in \text{ext } P} N(P, x) = \mathbb{R}^3$ as each support plane contains and extreme point of K ; hence $S_0(P, \omega) = \mathcal{L}^2(\omega)$. As each proper face of P is contained in an 2-dimensional face, and since the faces form a disjoint decomposition of the boundary of P , then $C_2(P, \beta) = \mathcal{L}^2(\beta \cap \text{bd } K)$. As $\dim F(K, u) \leq 1$, then we have $S_2(P, \beta) = \mathcal{L}^2(\cup_{u \in \omega} F(K, u)) = \mathcal{L}^2(\tau(K, u))$. For $K \in \mathcal{K}^3$ and $\beta \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^3)$ we define

$$\kappa(K, \beta) = \mathcal{L}^2(\sigma(K, \beta)) \quad (3.3)$$

By Proposition $\sigma(K, \beta)$ is a Lebesgue measurable subset of \mathbb{S}^2 . Let $\beta_1 \cap \beta_2 = \emptyset$. Let $u \in \sigma(K, \beta_1) \cap \sigma(K, \beta_2)$. This implies $H(K, u)$ contains a point of β_1 and β_2 . This implies $H(K, u) \cap K$ contains a point of β_1 and β_2 . Hence $F(K, u)$ has dimension greater than or equal to 1 because $\beta_1 \cap \beta_2 = \emptyset$ and thus $F(K, u)$ must contain more than 1 linearly independent points. Hence u is a singular vector by definition. Thus by Theorem we have

$$\mathcal{L}^2(\sigma(K, \beta_1 \cap \beta_2)) = 0$$

Since the restriction of \mathcal{L}^2 to the Lebesgue measurable subsets of \mathbb{S}^2 is σ -additive, it follows that $\kappa(K, \cdot)$ is a measure on $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^3)$. Let $(K_j)_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence in \mathcal{K}^3 converging to a convex body K . We take an open set $\beta \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ and assume that $u \in \sigma(K, \beta) \cap \text{regn } K$. $u \in \sigma(K, \beta) \cap \text{regn } K \Rightarrow u \in \cup_{x \in \beta} N(K, x)$ $x \in H(K, u)$ for some $x \in \beta$ $x \in H(K, u) \cap K = F(K, u)$ for some $x \in \beta$ $u \in \text{regn } K \Rightarrow \dim F(K, u) = 0$

Thus we conclude there exists a unique point $x \in F(K, u)$ where $x \in \beta$. Thus we can choose for $j \in \mathbb{N}$ $x_j \in F(K_j, u)$. Any accumulation point y of the sequence $(x_j)_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ lies in K as K is closed by virtue of being a convex body. $y \in H(K, u)$ \cdot $h(\cdot, u)$ is a continuous function. Thus $y \in F(K, u)$. As $F(K, u)$ has a unique point we conclude $y = x$. Thus $x_j \rightarrow x$ for $j \rightarrow \infty$ and, therefore $x_j \in \beta$ and $u \in \sigma(K_j, \beta)$ for almost all j . This shows that

$$\sigma(K, \beta) \cap \text{regn } K \subset \liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(K_j, \beta)$$

We know that the set of singular normal vectors have \mathcal{L}^2 measure 0. Hence we have

$$\begin{aligned}\kappa(K, \beta) &= \mathcal{L}^2(\sigma(K, \beta) \cap \text{regn } K) \leq \mathcal{L}^2(\liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(K_j, \beta)) \\ &\leq \liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{L}^2(\sigma(K_j, \beta)) = \liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} \kappa(\sigma(K_j, \beta))\end{aligned}$$

As β was chosen arbitrarily this result holds for all open sets in \mathbb{R}^3 . We know that $\bigcup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^3} N(K, x) = \mathbb{R}^3$ for any convex body in \mathbb{R}^3 . Hence $\kappa(K_j, \beta) = \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{S}^2) = \kappa(K_j, \beta)$. Thus we have proved the weak continuity $\kappa(K_j, \cdot) \xrightarrow{w} \kappa(K, \cdot)$. Thus the equality $\kappa(K, \cdot) = C_0(K, \cdot)$ follows immediately if K is approximated by a sequence of polytopes, since it is true for polytopes and both sides are weakly continuous. Next we put

$$\eta(K, \beta) = \mathcal{L}^2(\beta \cap \text{bd } K)$$

for $K \in \mathcal{K}_3^3$ and $\beta \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^3)$. Then $\eta(K, \cdot)$ is a measure since it is a restriction of a measure. It suffices to show that $K_j \rightarrow K$ implies $\eta(K_j, \cdot) \xrightarrow{w} \eta(K, \cdot)$. WLOG $o \in \text{int } K$ since measure is translation invariant and thus $\eta(K, \cdot)$ will not change. Define

$$\phi: \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus \{o\} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^2 \text{ by } \phi(x) := \frac{x}{|x|}$$

Let $\rho(K, \cdot)$ be the radial function such that for $y \in \mathbb{S}^2$ the point $\rho(K, y)y$ is a boundary point of K . Now,

$$\begin{aligned}\eta(K, \beta) &= \mathcal{L}^2(\beta \cap \text{bd } K) \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} 1_{\beta \cap \text{bd } K}(y) d\mathcal{L}^{n-1}(y)\end{aligned}$$

If we substitute $x = \phi(y)$ then applying Change of Variables formula we get

$$\eta(K, \beta) = \int_{\phi(\beta \cap \text{bd } K)} \frac{1}{\rho(K, y)^2} \det Ad \mathcal{L}^2(y)$$

where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - y_1^2 & -y_1 y_2 & \cdots & -y_1 y_3 \\ -y_1 y_2 & 1 - y_2^2 & \cdots & -y_2 y_3 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -y_1 y_3 & -y_2 y_3 & \cdots & 1 - y_3^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

□

where $y = (y_1, y_2, y_3) \in \mathbb{S}^2$. As radial function is continuous then the integrand is continuous and is bounded as well since $y \in \mathbb{S}^2$. Thus using Fatous's Lemma and Bounded Convergence Theorem we have $\eta(K_j, \cdot) \rightarrow \eta(K, \cdot)$ as $j \rightarrow \infty$. This completes the proof for $C_2(K, \beta)$.

Put

$$F(K, \omega) := \mathcal{L}^2(\tau(K, \omega))$$

for convex body K with interior points and $\omega \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S}^2)$. BY translation we may assume $o \in \text{int } K$. We know that $\phi(\tau(K, \omega))$ is Lebesgue measurable on \mathbb{S}^2 . If $\omega_1 \cap \omega_2 = \emptyset$, then

$$\mathcal{L}^2(\tau(K, \omega_1 \cap \tau(K, \omega_2))) = 0$$

. By applying the same argument as above we can conclude that $F(K_j, \cdot) \rightarrow F(K, \cdot)$ as $j \rightarrow \infty$.

Bibliography

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